

THE THEORY AND THE PRACTICE OF A NEW SCIENTIFIC DIRECTION

**TOPOLOGY OF THE BEGINNING OF VISIBLE AND INVISIBLE
MATTER**

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Abstract:

This Principle is enshrined in the law of natural numbers—the indisputable logic of its content, directly related to the fundamental data of physical definitions. In this case, it becomes true that Everything arose from Invisible Nothing and Visible Something. Light, combining properties determined by the genetic and physical perception of known fundamental data, represents the elementary structure of the organic and inorganic fusion of visible and invisible matter, forming a single common Space. These two principles, genetic and physical, are represented by the interconnection of discrete concentrations of dark and light matter, down to topological architectures relative to a single common density of superposition of their interaction. The proposed method for this interconnection is based on fundamental mathematical and physical constants, the interaction of which is based on the functional data of the external and internal space of a single Common Dark Matter. Based on this, an analysis of the consistency of the Higgs boson was conducted, defining the characteristics of the formation of mass-based and massless functional structures and their charges. Examples of phase interactions between compression and expansion processes of spatial units of volumes of general matter are presented. The proposed material radically changes the established understanding of the radioactive decays of nuclides in the open-volume structure of the expansion process. In this case, the direct functional relationship between visible and invisible matter is confirmed, with the subsequent generation of mass definitions.

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Subject:

According to the arithmetic operations of negative numbers, the equality of the projections of these values is determined by only two functional results of the interaction of the positive and negative signs of natural numbers. These are difference and multiplication. As is well known, in the case of addition of a positive and negative of the same argument, the result is zero: ($n^+ + n^- = 0$). In the second case, dividing these arguments equals minus one: ($n^+ / n^- = -1$). In his previous works, the author presented variants of interactions between the limits of the fundamental functions of external and internal space, subject to the conditions of the expansion process, that is, by dividing each argument by the sum of these arguments. This was due to the fact that a particular phase process of expansion determined the immediate essence of the functional structure of the "combination" of the fundamental limits of the space of "light" and "dark" matter relative to the primary volume: ($\pi/6$). In other words, the author merely provided a logical connection between fundamental mathematical and physical quantities under the conditions of the Cold Evolution of the Universe, without considering the position of common Matter. In this material, Dark Matter is presented as the Unified Common Matter of Space.

1. Superposition of the subject:

Any point you place on a sheet of paper will define its value as internal space. Thus, the concentration of an object is determined by the natural ordinate of a unit of space. Naturally, the visible materialization of a given object is only possible under the conditions of external space, that is, relative to the periphery of the sheet of paper's contour. In this case, the relationship between the internal and external spaces of the sheet of paper, since it is a plane, will correspond to a linear expression in which the value of volume is open. In this case, one should not deform the sheet of paper so that the external volume is represented by a single point of internal content. This is absurd! In the conditions of the absolute Space of the Universe, this absurdity acquires meaning, since the meaning of internal space, as a unit of volume, contains the fundamental conditions of linear and volumetric interactions with external space. This is the primary state of Dark Matter Space without defining its own point of internal content. This is also absurd, since the objectivity of any space is determined by its inherent subjectivity, that is, by some state. This is so because all the conditions for the content of internal space are embedded in a single structure—the unit of volume. These conditions are dictated by the fact that defining the external contour of Dark Matter Space is impossible, and therefore, the infinity of its possible dimensions leads to an infinity of points defined as units of internal space. Thus, knowing the fundamental metric of a unit of primary volume, in the form of the value of pi, defined as ($\pi/6$), it remains only to indicate the presence of the conditions for separating dark and light matter in the structure of its content. Since, in this case, the radius of this volume is equal to one, the power determining the values of the separated projections of dark and light matter will be equal to minus one, "Primary Volume Structure Matrix".

Primary Volume Structure Matrix

	Basis 1	Phase 1	Phase 2	Volume 1
A	0.5	0.125	0.392699082	0.065449847
	Basis 2	Phase 3	Phase 4	Volume 2
B	0.333333333	0.037037037	0.116355283	0.019392547
	Basis 3	Phase 5	Phase 6	Volume 3
C	0.166666666	0.004629630	0.014544410	0.002406800

As you can see, this is not a vacuum. At its core, it is a triple point of matter, defined by three bases, six phases, and three volumes. In the author's case, this structure represents the fundamental cause of the merging of the interactions between inner and outer space. Here, the functional phase transitions of a linear function to a volumetric one and vice versa occur.

And so, the negative "cold" numbers. They determine not only the limits of the bases of their projections of "warm" numbers, but also the result of these contents. This productive interaction of spatial structures is explained by the "collective" position of the "focus," a shift between opposing projections of the limits of "compression" and "expansion." For example, the third base of the "Primary Volume Structure Matrix," equal to the number field ($6^{-1} = 0.1666666666$), defines its projection with cold matter as the base of the third volume:

$$(1) \text{Ln}(0.002424068) = -6.0223079911$$

This base is the limit of the negative value of the reduced volume, the nucleon: (nykl), number of which represents the degree of the focal displacement relative to minus one:

$$(2) \text{nykl} \rightarrow -6.0223079911 / 6 = -1.00371799$$

In this case, the limit of the value of the "cold" nucleon determines the projection of the field of the unit "warm" matter:

$$(3) \exp(\text{nykl}) = 0.366514206$$

This number is the "field" of the value of the constant "e":

$$(4) e' \rightarrow (0.366514206)^{-1} = 2.728407208$$

In the case of a paired linear sequence, the "warm" projection of the negative nucleon number establishes a connection with the second base "Pi":

$$(5) \exp(\text{nykl})^2 \rightarrow 0.134332663 \rightarrow \exp(0.134332663) \rightarrow 1.143773247 \rightarrow \exp(1.143773247) = \text{Pi}'(3.138588722)$$

This isn't just an informational numerical relationship between known constants. For example, the value of the negative field power "e" reduces the cold base limit from minus one to minus two, the reduced base "Pi":

$$(6) \text{Ln}(e^{-1}) = -1$$

$$(7) \text{Ln}(e^{-2}) = -2 \rightarrow \exp(-2) \rightarrow \exp(0.135335283) \rightarrow \exp(1.144920593) \rightarrow \text{Pi}'(3.142191834)$$

For the static cold third base "Pi", in the periods of gradation of the value of the relationship between the internal and external space, the focus of the field of linear displacement of the symmetry structure of this limit will be a fragment of the function of the common proton of the mirror nuclei:

$$(8) [\exp(\exp(\exp(\text{Pi})))^{-1} \rightarrow -2.001231639^{-1} = \text{fmp} (-0.49969228)$$

Where, the exponent of this base will be the field of the neutron of the mirror nucleus of Oxygen (${}_8\text{O}^{16}$):

$$(9) \exp(\text{fmp})^2 \rightarrow 0.368105919^{-1} \rightarrow e'(2.716609403) \rightarrow \ln(e') = 0.99938456^{-1} \leftrightarrow \text{fnn} ({}_8\text{O}^{16}) (1.000615819)$$

Here, the difference between the cold limit of the proton fragment field base relative to the static symmetry of the interaction limit of the internal and external space will be:

$$(10) -2.001231639 - \ln(0.99938456^{-1}) = -2.000616009$$

In this case, it should be said that the dark matter field of the reduced proton forms a pair to a cubic degree according to the relation - the expansion of the interaction of number and field to the state of symmetry, Helium (${}^4_2\text{He}$):

$$(11) \quad ({}^4_2\text{He})' \rightarrow (-2.001231639 / \text{fmp}(-0.49969228)) = 4.00492807$$

Therefore, the value of the nucleon, the unit of composition, brings this content into cubic correspondence with the value of the third volume of the matrix "Primary Volume Structure Matrix":

$$(12) \quad \text{nykl} \rightarrow (4.00492807 / 4) \rightarrow \sqrt[3]{1.001232018} = 1.000615819$$

$$(13) \quad 1.001232018^2 = 1.002465553$$

$$(14) \quad \ln(1.002465553) = 0.002462519$$

Thus, the transformation of point (14) leads to the state of point (1). According to the sequence of inverse actions of the contents of the "Primary Volume Structure Matrix," the third base of the given third volume will correspond to the field definition:

$$(15) \quad [\sqrt[3]{((0.002462519 \cdot 6) / \text{Pi})}]^{-1} \rightarrow 5.968607369 / 6 = 0.994767895$$

First of all, this dark matter field contains basic information about the multifunctional linear relationship of this content. For example, the actual projection of this value leads to the static definition of the helium nucleon number (${}^4_2\text{He}$):

$$(16) \quad \text{nykl} ({}^4_2\text{He}) \rightarrow \sqrt[8]{(0.994767895^{-1})} \rightarrow 1.000655945 \rightarrow 4\text{nykl} = 4.00262378$$

The action of compression - multiplication, opposite to the position (11) of expansion, also determines the linear power of the value of the projection of the second position (2) of the negative nucleon number:

$$(17) \quad {}^4_2\text{He}' (4.00492807) \cdot -2.001231639 \rightarrow \text{nykl} (-8.014788764 / 8) = -1.001848596$$

$$(18) \quad \text{nykl}^2 = 1.003700609 \leftrightarrow \text{nykl} (2) = -1.00371799$$

Here, the square of the negative nucleon, as the root of the reduced proton, corresponds to the cubic value of the symmetry transformation node of the reduced Helium (${}^4_2\text{He}$)', (12):

$$(19) \quad (18) \sqrt[3]{(\text{nykl}^2 = 1.003700609)} \rightarrow \sqrt[3]{1.001232018} \rightarrow 1.000615819 (12)$$

In any case, these positions represent the interaction of the linear and cubic structure of one number of reduced protons:

$$(20) \quad \text{mp}' \rightarrow ((12) \text{nykl}^4)^3 = 1.007414909$$

The sum of the linear and cubic powers is the twelfth power, that is: (3 x 4), (6 x 2), represented by the subsequent definition of the nucleon number of the mirror nucleus of Carbon (${}^{12}_6\text{C}$):

$$(21) \quad \text{nykl} C \rightarrow \sqrt[4]{1.003700609 (18)} = 1.000923871 \rightarrow m({}_6\text{C}^{12}) = 12\text{nykl} C = 12.01108645$$

This is a quantum interaction, since all data are determined by the orders of the linear structures of cold - negative and positive paired bases of the category of electron metrics and positron superposition of the cen-

tral absolute symmetry, combining the concentration of the limits of internal and external space in one single point.

2. General topology of the object:

In the fundamental metric of the variable value "e" - proportional conditions containing mass definitions of physical quantities related to certain compositions of atomic weights, such as the ratio of the mass number to the charge number: $(m / z = e')$, and the ratio of the composition of protons to the composition of neutrons:

$$[(e' - 1) = n(mn) / n(mp) \leftrightarrow n(mp) / n(mn)].$$

First of all, this determines the material content of the functional operator of causes and conditions for the formation of a comparative topological dimensional space. In this case, there is no need to talk about the quantum Hall effect, since the two-dimensional electron and positron systems do not contain values of different polarities. This condition is determined by the separating fields—a function of dark matter.

The reason for this content is the superposition of the base unit: $(\ln(1) = 0)$. That is, the reason for the onset of supersymmetry is from the superposition of base zero, as: $\exp(0) \rightarrow 1!$ This is a positive number. Its mirror image, minus one, is determined by the constant field: $(\ln(e^{-1}) = -1)$. Naturally, their sum will correspond to the opposite action, that is, the difference: $(1 - (-1) = 2)$.

Here, the content of mirroring is the basis of this difference: $(\ln(2) = 0.693147181)$, that is, the second fragment of the negative field (e):

$$(\ln(0.693147181) = -0.366512921).$$

In turn, the field of this base already determines the “distortion” of the mirror image in the form of a negative, reduced (e'): $-0.366512921^{-1} = -2.728416773$.

This basis leads to the first volume (1V) of the “Primary Volume Structure Matrix”:

$$\exp(-2.728416773) = 0.065322628.$$

It should be noted that the value of the reduced volume number has several definitions. In one case, it is the number of the base event (e'), which corresponds to the value category of points (2) and (18), that is:

$$2e' \rightarrow 0.065322628^{-1} \rightarrow \ln(15.30863078) = 1.003721504.$$

In another case, this number is a node of transformation of numerical values that determine one of the main functions of interaction between internal and external space, in particular, this is a function of the proton, the number of the third volume and the central value of the connection between the limits of proton and neutron fragments:

$$(22) \text{ mp}' \rightarrow 1.003721504^2 = 1.007456858 \leftrightarrow {}^3V = \ln({}^3\sqrt{\text{mp}'}) \rightarrow \mathbf{0.002476398} \leftrightarrow {}^6\sqrt{1.003721504} \rightarrow (19)$$

Here, (3V) is the third volume of the Primary Volume Structure Matrix. For a more precise determination of positions (12) and (21), the bonds between the Carbon and Helium nucleons will be as follows:

$$(23) \text{ nykl C} \rightarrow {}^4\sqrt{1.003721504} = 1.000929081 \leftrightarrow 12\text{nykl C} = m({}_6\text{C}^{12}) \rightarrow 12.01114897$$

For the conditions of the Helium nucleon, the base of the reduced first volume should be determined:

$$(24) \text{ mykl He} \rightarrow \sqrt[3]{((^1V \cdot 6) / \text{Pi})} = \text{fmp}' \rightarrow (2\text{fmp}')^{-1} = 1.00064876 \leftrightarrow 4\text{mykl He} \rightarrow m(^2\text{He}^4) = 4.002595038$$

In contrast to the conditions of a spatial point, where the gradation of the bases of pi determines the superposition of internal space, the conditions (e) – units of space distribute the values of dark and light matter as mirror projections of the main functional fragments of internal and external space. This is why the base of the nucleon of mirror helium is defined as the intermediate value of the number of degrees of freedom between the functional fragments of the proton and neutron of the mirror nucleus of oxygen ($^8\text{O}^{16}$). Helium itself ($^2\text{He}^4$) is only third after mirror nitrogen ($^7\text{N}^{14}$). This is explained, first of all, by the order of the natural numbers seven and eight, the ratio of which determines the first base of pi:

$$(25) \text{ Pi}' \rightarrow \exp(8 / 7) = 3.135714764$$

Here, the essence of these interactions should be explained in more detail. The relationship of the numerical structures seven and eight is like a combination of a sum; for seven, three plus four: ($3 + 4 = 7$), and for eight: ($4 + 4 \rightarrow 2^3 = 8$), is defined as a cyclic structure of nodal relationships between cubic and linear expressions of spatial limits. In this case, the superposition of this relationship can be represented by the second—the average volume (2V)—of the "Primary Volume Structure Matrix":

$$(26) \ ^2V = \ln(\ln(8 / 7)) \rightarrow -2.013418678^{-1} \rightarrow \exp(-0.496667688) \rightarrow 0.60855518^8 = 0.018810473$$

In this case, the relationship between the mirror units of space follows from the linear definition:

$$(27) \ln(\ln(8 / 7)) \rightarrow -2.013418678 \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}(-2.013418678) = -1.006709339$$

$$(28) \ e' \rightarrow (\sqrt{\ln(8 / 7)})^{-1} = 2.736581022 \leftrightarrow \ln(2.736581022) = 1.00670939$$

The linear base of the given unit of space will be the neutron number of the mirror nucleus of Nitrogen ($^7\text{N}^{14}$) to the fourth power:

$$(29) \text{ mn}' (^7\text{N}^{14}) \rightarrow \sqrt[4]{\ln(e')} = 1.001673131$$

After which, explanatory decisions follow:

$$(30) \text{ m} (^7\text{N}^{14}) \rightarrow (7 \cdot \text{mp}'(0.999311456)) + (7 \cdot \text{mn}'(1.001673131)) = 14.00689211$$

$$(31) \text{ mykl He} \rightarrow \exp(\text{fmn}' (^8\text{O}^{16}) - \text{fmp}' (^8\text{O}^{16})) \rightarrow \exp(0.50030689 - 0.499655610) = 1.000651493$$

Here, position (30) refers to the determination of the mass of the mirror nucleus of Nitrogen ($^7\text{N}^{14}$). Position (31) confirms position (24), which is related to the determination of the nucleon number of Helium ($^2\text{He}^4$).

The sequence of these definitions is such that the degree of freedom is an intermediate value, the relationship of the functional fragments of mirror Helium ($^2\text{He}^4$) is the central basis of the relationship of the static neutron to the static proton:

$$(32) \text{ mn} / \text{mp} \rightarrow \exp(\text{fmn}' - \text{fmp}') = 1.001378511 \leftrightarrow 1.001339678$$

- $\text{mn} = 1,008665012, \text{mp} = 1,00727647, \text{fmn}' = 0.50099439, \text{fmp}' = 0.49965561$

Naturally, static and dynamic conditions produce slightly different interaction results. In this case, the results of functional interactions between the basic functions of the reduced proton and neutron are demonstrated under the conditions of the exchange phase: $((A+B)/A)^{-1}$, where the expansion occurs relative to the proton fragment function "A".

Therefore, the neutron fragment function is "B." Unlike the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen (EPR) paradox, which lacks the concept of the structure of the primary volume, defined by them as a quantum entangled state, superpositions of mirror spatial units contain fundamental values of physical weights. Thus, the contour values of nucleons—the units of charge of nuclear symbols—belong to the category of actual functional reality. In this case, the method of functional interaction of the main functions of internal and external space, previously proposed by the author, as the ratio of phase definitions of proton and neutron fragments, under conditions of mirror limits of spatial units, remains only a “visible” fair result of the processes of compression and expansion of the structures of the nucleon composition.

These conditions are satisfied taking into account mass definitions, where the nucleon number value remains constant for the entire series of isotopes of the same nuclear symbol. In the case of mirror units, whose conditions are linked by parallel spaces of visible and invisible matter, the values of the negative bases—the quantum limits of the gradational levels of transitions in the relationship between linear and cubic values—are not constant. This introduces a significant correction to the existing knowledge of superconductivity at low temperatures. The main incompatibility of the desired concepts of the imaginary condensation of Cooper pairs is that the positive combination of electrons and positrons determines the degree of motion of the hypothetical processes of compression or expansion relative to the phase state of the mass functional structure. Meanwhile, the negative combination of polar charge carriers shapes the composition of the hypothetical nucleon as a single charge of this mass structure. In this case, the exception is the very principle of localization of such a pair, even in the split Pauli structure, where the intermediate constant is supposedly the atomic nucleus, that is, a certain concentrated density resulting from the interaction of charges, better known as the gravitational or electromagnetic component of matter. First and foremost, this is a quantitative linear and cubic structure, combining the functional limits of two fundamental opposing processes: compression and expansion. Thus, the conditions of pairs in a linear sequence define the quantum structure of the order of interaction (combination) between a number and its field, as the content of visible and invisible reality within the limits of the series—the event horizon—until the complete fusion of these values. For example, the pair of the sum of a number and its field of a static proton:

$$(33) \quad mp(1.00727647) + mp^{-1}(0.992776095) = 2.000052565$$

The set of arguments of the degree of quantum interactions, relative to the unit of total space (e'), as a combination of dark and light matter for these values, will initially amount to one half of the sum of the number and the field of the proton:

$$(34) \quad e' = [\exp \rightarrow (\frac{1}{2}(2.000052565)) \rightarrow 1.000026282] = 2.718353272$$

Next, the cubic power relates this unit to the constant unit of volume ($\text{Pi} / 6$):

$$(35) \quad (e')^3 = 20.08712067$$

Here, the number of events of the “open”, unfinished volume (35) will constitute an intermediate value in the structure of the given projection ($\text{Pi} / 6$)” of the unit of volume ($\text{Pi} / 6$):

$$(36) \quad (\text{Pi} / 6)'' \rightarrow (35)^{-1} \rightarrow 0.049783143 \leftrightarrow (1 - 0.049783143) \rightarrow (0.950216857 / 2) = 0.475108429$$

The ratio between the fundamental and reduced units of volume (Pi / 6) and (Pi / 6)' leads to the value of the third volume (${}^3\mathbf{V}$) of the Primary Volume Structure Matrix:

$$(37) \quad (\text{Pi} / 6)' \rightarrow (1 - (\text{Pi} / 6)'') = 0.54891571 \leftrightarrow {}^3\mathbf{V}' \rightarrow \ln(0.54891571 / (\text{Pi} / 6)) = 0.002466015$$

But, the basis of this volume is the field value of the composition of the structure of the primary volume:

$$(38) \quad \text{Basis } 3' \rightarrow [{}^3\sqrt{(({}^3\mathbf{V}' \cdot 6) / \text{Pi})}]^{-1} = 5.965785526 \leftrightarrow 5.965785526 / 6 = 0.994297588$$

In this case, the third volume number, as already mentioned, is the cubic base of the reduced proton number (mp'):

$$(39) \quad \text{mp}' \rightarrow (\exp({}^3\mathbf{V}'))^3 = 1.007425478$$

Specifically, for reference, the nucleon number of this definition has two primary meanings for this topic. First, it is the square root of the reduced neutron number:

$$(40) \quad \text{nykl}' \rightarrow ((e')^3 / 20) = 1.004356034 \leftrightarrow \text{mn}' \rightarrow (\text{nykl}')^2 = 1.008731042$$

Secondly, the base of the eighth root of the cyclic power of a given nucleon leads to the reduced value of the electron mass number:

$$(41) \quad 'm_e \rightarrow \ln({}^8\sqrt{\text{nykl}'}) = 0.000543322$$

The degree (st^n) of quantum definitions itself, within the matrix of nine-digit values of the sums of linear pairwise combinations of the number and field of the fundamental proton, comes from the "open" reduced volume of position (35), which is the basis of this degree:

$$(42) \quad st^n \rightarrow \exp((e')^3) = 529328970$$

Thus, returning to the linear transformation of the pair - the sum of the number and the field of the number of the fundamental proton, determined by position (33), then the corresponding final solution of this limit will be a nine-digit periodic value of the absolute fusion of these arguments:

$$(43) \quad {}^{529328970}\sqrt{2.000052565} = 1.000000001309530$$

In this case, the limit (lim^{-n}) and the field (n^{-1}) of the negative base will be:

$$(44) \quad \text{lim}^{-n} \rightarrow \ln(\ln(1.000000001309530)) = -20.45359565 \leftrightarrow n^{-1} \rightarrow -20.45359565^{-1} = -0.048891159$$

Two peculiarities of these results should be noted here. The first peculiarity, related to the negative base of the limit (lim^{-n}) of the linear orders of position (43), pertains to the contents of the table of linear limits, "Table of linear limits of number and field of number." Here, in the table of linear limits, column (N) represents the basic composition of natural numbers. Column (Lim^+) corresponds to the positive limit of one-tenth of the composition unit, taken as the basis of the counting limit. Next, column ($\ln^{(\text{Lim}^+)}$) defines the limit of the negative base unit of the composition of natural numbers. Then, column ($n^{\ln(\text{Lim}^+)}$) is the sum field of the units of the composition: $N(\ln(\text{Lim}^+))$.

Table of linear limits of number and field of number

N	Lim ⁺	ln(Lim ⁺)	n ^{ln(Lim)}	exp(n ^{ln(Lim)})	ln(Lim)'	exp(ln(Lim)')	exp ²	(exp ²) ²
1	0.1	-2.30258509	-0.434294482	0.64772148514	-2.302585093	0,1		
2	0.1	-2.30258509	-4.605170186	0.01	-0.217147241	0.804811459	0.647721485	0.419543122
3	0.1	-2.30258509	-6.907755279	0.001	-0.144764827	0.865225747	0.748615593	0.560425306
4	0.1	-2.30258509	-9.210340372	0.0001	-0.10857362	0.897112847	0.804811459	0.647721485
5	0.1	-2.30258509	-11.51292546	0.00001	-0.086858896	0.916806451	0.840534069	0.706497521
6	0.1	-2.30258509	-13.81551056	0.000001	-0.072382414	0.930175116	0.865225747	0.748615593
7	0.1	-2.30258509	-16.11809565	0.0000001	-0.062042069	0.939843348	0.883305518	0.780228639
8	0.1	-2.30258509	-18.42068074	0.00000001	-0.05428681	0.947160412	0.897112847	0.804811459
9	0.1	-2.30258509	-20.72326584	0.000000001	-0.048254942	0.952890824	0.908000922	0.824465675
			sum n ^{ln(Lim)}	sum (Lim ⁻)	sum ⁻¹		exp(ln(Lim)')	exp(ln(Lim)')

Then the next column ($\exp(n^{\ln(\text{Lim})})$) establishes limits according to the composition of natural numbers. The column ($\ln(\text{Lim})'$) maps the transformed sums to the limits of the ordinal period fields of the composition of natural numbers. Thus, the column ($\exp(\ln(\text{Lim})')$) returns the transformed periods to the positive limits of the number fields of the unit composition of natural numbers. Finally, the columns (\exp^2) and $((\exp^2)^2)$ define a direct linear relationship between the transformed limits of the general array of the underlying composition of natural numbers. Thus, comparing the previous solutions with the data in the proposed table, a second feature of the presented data for the solution points should be noted. Specifically, this is practically the same result as the data on the finite limits of the "fusion" of the number and the number field of the fundamental proton, point (44), and the maximum sum of units of the composition of natural numbers, column ($\text{sum } n^{\ln(\text{Lim})}$): $-20.72326584 \leftrightarrow -20.45359565$. In practical terms, given the functional matrix composition based on the table presented, this content allows for the "expanding" of spatial boundaries for defining and forming mass numbers. This capability completely eliminates the traditional notion of the quantum structure of the numerical composition of a nuclear symbol. For example, the known number of protons and neutrons in the Oxygen nucleon, their quantity, determines the finite number of this composition of the mirror nucleus of Oxygen (${}_8\text{O}^{16}$). Its unit of composition (Lim^+) is the sum of the reduced proton number and the reduced neutron number, where the number is the neutron (mn') and the field of the number is the proton (mp'):

(45) $\text{Lim}^+ \rightarrow \text{mn}'(1.00061378) + \text{mp}'(0.99931122) = 1.999925$

As a result, this number is one half of the mass ($\frac{1}{2} m$) of Oxygen (${}_8\text{O}^{16}$):

(46) $\frac{1}{2}m \rightarrow 8(\text{Lim}^+) = 15.9994$

From this it follows that the field of a given unit of composition leads to the number of nucleons of this mass, with the subsequent definition of the actual, whole unit of composition:

(47) $n^{-1} \rightarrow (45), \frac{1}{2}(\text{Lim}^+) \leftrightarrow \text{nykl}({}_8\text{O}^{16}) = 0.9999625$

Thus, the negative limit (Lim^-) of a unit of composition will be its base:

(48) $\text{Lim}^- \rightarrow \ln(\text{nykl}({}_8\text{O}^{16})) = -0.000037501$

The square of this base leads to the base of the final sum of the reduced units of composition within the given limits:

(49) $(\text{Lim}^-)^2 \rightarrow 0.000000001406303 \leftrightarrow n^{\ln(\text{Lim})} \rightarrow \ln((\text{Lim}^-)^2) = -20.38230155$

Below is information on the transformation of numbers and values in the context of proposed practical problems related to quantum computing to determine spatial units of mass and mass numerical structures.

It should be clarified that, as you can see, in the presented examples, there is no quantum entanglement for

the interaction conditions of an electron and positron. In this presentation, these particles refer to the bases of the reduced protons and neutrons of paragraph (45), in particular, from paragraph (41), these values in the composition of the mirror nucleus of Oxygen (${}_8\text{O}^{16}$) will be the bases of the reduced proton and neutron:

$$(50) \quad m^{e^-} \rightarrow \ln(mp') = -0.000689017 \leftrightarrow m^{e^+} \rightarrow \ln(mn') = 0.000613592$$

The third feature of the proposed table of contents, "Table of linear limits of number and field of number," is the final column content ($\ln(\text{Lim})'$), which displays the transformed sums of negative bases into limits of fields of ordinal periods of the composition of natural numbers. Specifically, in this example, we will discuss the value of the column number: ($\sum n^{\ln(\text{Lim})} = -0.048254942$), the limit of the entire composition of natural numbers. This number is directly related to the linear and cubic relationships in the structure of the unit volume ($\text{Pi}/6$). First and foremost, this number, as a fundamental definition, relates to the units of volume and space, the constants (e) and ($\text{Pi}/6$). It is an intermediate value—the degree of freedom of the value of the unit volume ($\text{Pi}/6$) within the unit:

$$(51) \quad (e^3)^{-1} \rightarrow (1 - (\text{Pi}/6)) = 0.476401224 \leftrightarrow (\text{Pi}/6) - 0.476401224 = 0.047197551$$

In this case, the cubic base unit of space (e') corresponds to the given value of the square root of the neutron number (mn'):

$$(52) \quad e' \rightarrow \sqrt[3]{(0.047197551)^{-1}} = 2.767112681 \leftrightarrow mn' \rightarrow \sqrt{\ln(2.767112681)} = 1.008862936$$

To do this, two given variants of the relationship between fundamental physical values must be determined. The first variant, when the square of the sum of the bases of the column: ($\sum n^{\ln(\text{Lim})} = -20.72326584$), from the table "Table of linear limits of number and field of number," determines the quantitative (n^{\leftrightarrow}) linear relationship of the mirror limits of intermediate values ($v \leftrightarrow v'$) of units ($e^- \leftrightarrow e^+$) of the volumes of visible and invisible space:

$$(53) \quad e^- \leftrightarrow e^+ = \frac{-20.72326584^2}{\sqrt{(n^{\leftrightarrow} 429.4537469)}} \leftarrow \frac{20.72326584^{-1}}{\sqrt{(n^{\leftrightarrow} 429.4537469)}} = v \leftrightarrow v'(0.048254942)$$

Here, the base ($\ln(e')$) of the reduced unit (e') of space leads the linear sequence, again, to point (31) of the Helium nucleon:

$$(54) \quad (\ln(e')) \rightarrow \ln(\ln(\sqrt[3]{20.72326584})) = 1.010419007 \leftrightarrow \text{nykl}(\text{He}) \rightarrow \sqrt[16]{1.010419007} = 1.000648029$$

$$(55) \quad m({}_2\text{He}^4) \rightarrow 4\text{nykl}(\text{He}) = 4.002592115$$

Then, the presence of the Oxygen nucleon number, in the given content of the central interaction of fundamental values, comes from the number (n^s) of the event (n^{\leftrightarrow}) of the number of the interconnection of the linear sequence, where this number is the periodic formation of four pairs of the sixteenth power:

$$(56) \quad n^s \rightarrow 429.4537469^{-1} = 0.002328539 \leftrightarrow \text{nykl O} \rightarrow [(\exp(0.002328539))^{16}]^{-1} = 0.999963617$$

For general comparison:

$$(57) \quad m({}_8\text{O}^{16}) \rightarrow 16\text{nykl O} = 15.99941788$$

3. Specific topology of the object:

The presented positions, defining a particular relationship between known constants, follow certain rules for the interaction of units of spatial structures under the conditions of the formation of mass numbers.

This story is primarily associated with numerical events (ns) – the numbers of bases between the positive and negative values of any matter. They form the numerical composition of the nucleon structure.

This structure contains a state of separated superposition, uniting the quantum feature of the "fusion" of the spatial boundaries of dark and light matter. To begin, it is worth paying attention to the contents of the "Matrix of Perpendicular Orders of Natural Numbers." This static content of the proposed matrix determines the basic superposition of the equality of the sums of the compositions of natural numbers separated by a period (E'), one half of the sum of which determines the number of a nucleon containing two units of volume.

Matrix of perpendicular orders of natural numbers												
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	Sum and difference between periods	
n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	← Composition of numbers	
A'	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	period sum [A']	
B'	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0		period sum [B']	
C'	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0			period sum [C']	
D'	4	4	4	4	4	4	0				period sum [D']	
E'	5	5	5	5	5	0					period sum [E']	
F'	6	6	6	6	0						period sum [F']	
G'	7	7	7	0							period sum [G']	
H'	8	8	0								period sum [H']	
I'	9	0									period sum [I']	
J'	0										↓ Difference	
	45	36	28	21	15	10	6	3	1	0	Sum of periods →	
	Sum and values of periods										165	16 X 16

(58) $nykl^{(\text{sum}E')} \rightarrow (25 / 2) \rightarrow 12.5 / 12 = 1.041666667 \leftrightarrow 2v'(1.041666667 / 2) = 0.520833333$

In the first case, the static content of the nucleon number: (1.041666667), to the power of the number of one of the sums of the periods (B'and H'), equal to sixteen, determines the number of the reduced neutron (mn'), according to the Dalton metric, for the mirror nucleus of Carbon (${}_6C^{12}$):

(59) $mn'({}_6C^{12}) \rightarrow \sqrt[16]{1.041666667} = 1.002554632 \leftrightarrow 6mn' + 6mp'(0.99931122) = m({}_6C^{12}) 12.01119653$

Here, the Carbon nucleon number is represented by the event number (n^s) of the base of the sum of sums of the entire composition of the "Matrix of perpendicular orders of natural numbers":

(60) $n^s \rightarrow (165 / 5) \rightarrow 33^{-1} = 0.03030303$

(61) $nykl C \rightarrow \exp(((165 / 5)^{-1}))^2 = 1.000918274 \leftrightarrow 12(nykl C) \rightarrow m'({}_6C^{12}) = 12.01102435$

To more fully understand the meaning of the mathematical and physical values defined by these points, the following should be noted. The fundamental distinction between the proposed concepts of linear and cubic definitions lies in the principle of the structure of even and odd numbers. This is the natural separation of the nucleon number from the ratio of mass to mass number. However, in the case of defining the central division of the mass number into the ratio of the number and the number field, a certain shift in the central distribution of the interaction of these concepts arises. This means that dividing odd numbers into equal parts determines the central nucleon number as the value of two primary volumes. Dividing even numbers into equal parts, in turn, determines unity as the central nucleon number. In both cases, the degree of shift is determined by the quantum bases of the number fields of these values. In this case, the number field represents a comparison with the soil in which a tree grows, containing a visible, branched crown on the surface and an invisible root system underground. For a more complete presentation, a table of numbers, bases and numerical fields of nucleons is provided, taken from the content of the "Matrix of perpendicular orders of natural numbers" in table "A" of the numerical structure of nucleons within the mass numbers: 13 – 12. And so, as you can see, a conditional scale (M:0.1) is presented, a consistent relationship between the limits of mass numbers: (13 ↔ 12), with a central number: ($m^n = 12.5$), period (E'), "Matrix of perpendicular orders of natural numbers". In this case, the entire column: ("A"(Pi /6)'), represented as one-half of a nucleon: (1/2 nykl), refers to the positive units of the reduced volumes. In this definition, the projection relationship between the

numbers and the fields of these numbers is not determined, since this is a layered structure of the outer and inner volumes of a single nucleon number.

Table "A" of the numerical structure of nucleons within the range of mass numbers: 13 – 12

M:0.1	nykl	"A"(Pi / 6)'	"A" (Pi / 6)'		1/2 "A"	"B" (Pi / 6)'	
m ⁿ	m ⁿ / 12	1/2 nykl	(Pi / 6)	← Ln	"B"(Pi / 6)	(Pi / 6)	← Ln'
13	1.083333	0.54166667	1.03450713	0.0339251	0.5172536	0.98788154	-0.0121925
12.9	1.075000	0.5375	1.02654938	0.0262031	0.5132747	0.98028245	-0.0199145
12.8	1.066667	0.53333333	1.01859164	0.0184209	0.5092958	0.97268336	-0.0276967
12.7	1.058333	0.52916667	1.01063389	0.0105777	0.5053169	0.96508427	-0.0355399
12.6	1.050000	0.525	1.00267614	0.0026726	0.5013381	0.95748519	-0.043445
12.5	1.041667	0.52083333	0.99471839	-0.0052956	0.4973592	0.9498861	-0.0514132
12.4	1.033333	0.51666667	0.98676065	-0.0133278	0.4933803	0.94228701	-0.0594454
12.3	1.025000	0.5125	0.9788029	-0.021425	0.4894015	0.93468792	-0.0675426
12.2	1.016667	0.50833333	0.97084515	-0.0295883	0.4854226	0.92708883	-0.0757059
12.1	1.008333	0.50416667	0.96288741	-0.0378188	0.4814437	0.91948974	-0.0839364
12	1.000000	0.5	0.95492966	-0.0461176	0.4774648	0.91189065	-0.0922352
sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum
124.6	10.38333	5.19166667	9.91535295	-0.0879767	4.9576765	9.46846461	-0.5491527

The division of the reduced units of volumes comes from the coordination of the periodic relations of the basic reference unit of volume (Pi / 6) in the central period (E'), "Matrix of perpendicular orders of natural numbers" column: $(\frac{"A"(Pi / 6)'}{(Pi / 6)})$. Further, the logarithm of this transition, the number - the number field, determines the actual base in the column: (← Ln), by the number: (-0.0052956). In principle, this is the main shift relative to the fundamental physical data, in particular, the unit of the nucleon of Hydrogen (H¹): nykl H¹ = 1.00794. In this case, it is necessary to set out in more detail the essence of the content of the proposed table of numbers, bases and numerical fields of nucleons. Thus, the value of the number: (0.99471839), the reduced field of the second pair of the column: $(\frac{"A"(Pi / 6)'}{(Pi / 6)})$, the volume of the inner layer, the number of the nucleon of two outer reduced units of volumes: (1.041667), for a visible definition, will be:

$$(62) \quad (m^n \leftrightarrow 12.5) \rightarrow (\frac{"A"(Pi / 6)'}{(Pi / 6)}) \rightarrow 0.99471839^{-1} = 1.005309654 \leftrightarrow 1.00267614 \leftarrow (m^n \leftrightarrow 12.6)$$

Naturally, the degree of transition (stⁿ), number – field of number, between periods of a given scale of a numerical event (M:0.1), will be a negative value:

$$(63) \quad st^n \rightarrow \ln(1.00267614) / \ln(0.99471839) = -0,50467665$$

In turn, the positive number of this negative base of the degree of transition (stⁿ) will be the value that determines the following linear "transformation" of definitions:

$$(64) \quad \exp(st^n) = 0.603700753^2 \rightarrow e'(0.364454599)^2 \rightarrow \exp(0.132827155) \rightarrow \exp(1.142052583) = Pi'(3.133192908)$$

Further, the ratio of the displacement of superpositions between pi (Pi) and the reduced pi' (Pi') will correspond to the number: (1.00267614), column: $\frac{"A"(Pi / 6)'}{(Pi / 6)}$, period: (mn = 12.6):

$$(65) \quad Pi / Pi' = 1.00268089 \leftrightarrow 1.00267614$$

In this case, as you can see, the "node" of interaction between number fields and the bases of known constants is represented in linear and cubic content, located within the structure of a unit of established scale (M:0.1). As you can see, this quantum content does not require the traditional representation of extremely small quantities of this concept. Thus, continuing with what we started, the result of the superposition shift

between pi (Pi) and pi' (Pi') will be a nucleon of the mass of Hydrogen (H¹) in the following definition of linear and cubic interaction:

$$(66) \quad m(\text{nykl})H^1 \rightarrow \sqrt[6]{[2((\text{Pi} / 6) \cdot (\sqrt{1.00268089}))]} = 1.0079407$$

Here, it is also worth noting that the sums of the differences of the remaining periods of the "Matrix of perpendicular orders of natural numbers" are separated by the central period: (E' = 0). In particular, the event number: (n^s → 16⁻¹ = 0.0625), is the first volume (v¹) in the structure of two units of volume (Pi / 6), where the first base (Basis 1) will be the internal volume ([↓]v):

$$(67) \quad \text{Basis 1} \rightarrow \sqrt[3]{(6n^s / \text{Pi})} = \downarrow v (0.492372511)$$

In this case, the base of the given volume, as can be seen, is also the number of the next volume. This is a cyclic sequence, which largely relates to the genetic nature of the continuous functions of protein structures. For the proposed topic, the topology of the subject, the connection between mathematical and physical definitions in the process of division and formation of linear and volumetric pairs represents a combination of supersymmetries and superpositions with respect to the fundamental data of physical quantities. Naturally, the superposition will be in a period of reorientation of the defining values of number and field, internal and external space, positive and negative charge, and positive and negative base units of the volume structure. Thus, the linear content of the external volume, or rather, its field projection, will correspond to the square of the proton's "transition" number (p')

$$(68) \quad 2(\downarrow v) \rightarrow (\downarrow v)^{-1} = 2.030982595 \leftrightarrow \uparrow v = 1.015491298 \leftrightarrow \sqrt{\uparrow v} \rightarrow p' = 1.007715882$$

After which, it should be explained that the cubic root of a given proton is equal to the number of neutrons (mn) of the mirror nucleus of Carbon (⁶C¹²):

$$(69) \quad mn(\text{}^6\text{C}^{12}) \rightarrow \sqrt[3]{mp^{\leftrightarrow}} = 1.002565374$$

Then, completing the analysis of the first basis given, point (68), the cube of the transition proton (p') leads to two primary volumes, (Pi / 6):

$$(70) \quad (\text{Pi} / 6) \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}((\downarrow v)^3) \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}(p'^3) = 0.523598776$$

Another metric feature of the proposed Table "A" of the numerical structure of nucleons within the mass numbers 13 – 12 is the information in the column (mn), related to the sum of the period compositions (sum = 124.6). In the functional meaning of the established scale, the entire numerical structure of this table belongs to the quantitative (kol) of the shifted base of the Hydrogen nucleon (H¹).

In this case, the resulting sum is also subject to the determination of its two nucleons. These are the nucleon number of visible matter (nykl[°]) and the nucleon number of invisible matter (nykl[•]):

$$(71) \quad (\text{nykl}^\circ) \rightarrow (124.6 / 124) = 1.00483871$$

The resulting result represents a double content of actions. First, it is the square of the base of the reduced third volume (³V') of the "Primary Volume Structure Matrix":

$$(72) \quad \sqrt[3]{V'} \rightarrow \ln(\sqrt{1.00483871}) = 0.002413521$$

The sequence of operations that brings this result to the third base (Basis' 3) of the matrix "Primary Volume Structure Matrix" corresponds to the following value of the number of the given content:

$$(73) \quad \text{Basis' 3} \rightarrow \sqrt[3]{((6^3 V') / \text{Pi})} = 0.166424586 \leftrightarrow (\text{Basis' 3})^{-1} = 6.008727563$$

Here, the number of nucleons (${}^3\text{nykl}$), the given basic third number of the “Primary Volume Structure Matrix” will be the following value:

$$(74) \quad {}^3\text{nykl} \rightarrow 6.008727563 / 6 = 1.001454594$$

This number, according to the central definition of supersymmetry "Matrix of perpendicular orders of natural numbers", to the fifth power, leads to the value of the proton number ('mp):

$$(75) \quad 'mp \rightarrow ({}^3\text{nykl})^5 = 1.007294158$$

In the story of the third volume (3V) of the position (72), this proton has a slightly different definition:

$$(76) \quad "mp (\exp({}^3V))^3 = 1.007266839$$

In any case, the principle of distribution of quantitative structures by the numbers of nucleons, into visible and invisible values of the general state of matter, is defined as the unit of the charge base of a given structure. Thus, the determined sum (124.6) of the composition of periodic nucleons of Table "A" of the numerical structure of nucleons within the mass numbers: 13 - 12, is represented by a shifted value of the established scale (0.1) in favor of the shift of the quantitative mass number one hundred twenty-five (125) relative to the position (71). Consequently, in this case, the nucleon (nykl^\bullet) is considered as internal, invisible matter:

$$(77) \quad \text{nykl}^\bullet \rightarrow (124.6 / 125) = 0.9968$$

This field of the number, the square root to the fifth power brings it to the base – the event number (n^s) of the sum of the composition of periodic nucleons of the table “A” of the numerical structure of nucleons within the limits of mass numbers: 13 – 12:

$$(78) \quad \ln((\sqrt[5]{\text{nykl}^{\bullet-1}}))^5 \rightarrow n^s(0.0080'_{12828}) \leftrightarrow (n^s)^{-1} \rightarrow \text{kol}' = 124.799889$$

Naturally, the uncertainty determines a more precise scale of nucleon composition within given mass number limits. For example, by inverse calculation:

$$(79) \quad \sqrt[5]{(\exp(124.6^{-1}))} \rightarrow 1.00160425^2 \rightarrow 1.00321543^{-1} \cdot 125 = 124.5993593 (124.6)$$

In this case, the key role is played by the value of the reduced number of the neutron: ($\text{mn}' \rightarrow 1.00160425$), the mirror nucleus of Nitrogen (${}_{7}\text{N}^{14}$). In conditions of actual physical masses, this adjustment of the limits is determined automatically, based on the known ratio of mass to mass number. But, in this case, Table "A" of the numerical structure of nucleons within the limits of mass numbers: 13 - 12, we are talking about the quantum structure of the central superposition of the interaction of visible and invisible matter within a unit volume. The main indicator of this interaction is the reorientation of the relationship between the bases of the number and the field between the sixth and fifth periods of the column: ($\leftarrow \text{Ln}$), $(\frac{0.0026726}{-0.0052956})$.

This is natural if we take into account that the difference in the reorientation limits determines the event number (n^s) of the center of superposition of the entire composition of nucleons:

$$(80) \quad n^s \rightarrow (-0.0052956 - 0.0026726) = 0.00796817$$

In this case, the established event number (n^s), intermediate, shifted by the base of one-half the sum of the static proton and static neutron:

$$(81) \quad 2\exp(n^s) \rightarrow 2.016000001 \leftrightarrow 2.016000001 - \text{mp}(1.00727647) = \text{mn}(1.008723531)$$

In the following case, the event number quantity (n^s), the reduced value of the nucleon structure of Hydrogen (H^1), determined by the supersymmetry bias, possibly leads to the actual neutral "mass" of the imaginary Higgs boson (H^0):

$$(82) \quad m(H^0) \rightarrow (n^s)^{-1} = 125.4993305$$

It would be possible if the formation of this definition did not take place under conditions of superposition of spatial units of volume.

4. The "desired" object of Higgs boson topology or a flickering photon?

This is a static structure of the model of a "flickering" photon of the periods of reorientation of the central superposition: ($\leftarrow Ln$), ($\frac{0.0026726}{-0.0052956}$), the relationship of the internal and external space, which contains a layered volumetric "point-bubble" background of the numerical spectrum of the main spatial functions of the proton and neutron. It should be noted here that these are functions, not numbers, since a function can have and impart its effect to any number. This definition omits concepts such as wave function, charge, and electromagnetism. The periodic orders of the established numbers of nucleons are contained within the same boundaries of the general contour of the given structure. These are the inner ($\leftarrow Ln$) and outer ($\leftarrow Ln'$) layers of columns, equal in sum but different in value: ($\leftarrow Ln \leftrightarrow \leftarrow Ln'$). In this definition, the outer layer of column bases: ($\leftarrow Ln'$), double reduced units of column volumes: ($"B" \left(\frac{"B" (Pi / 6)'}{(Pi / 6)} \right)$), obtained as a result of the ratio to the primary volume: ($Pi / 6$), as functional fragments of the column proton and neutron: ($\frac{1/2 "A"}{"B" (Pi / 6)}$), is consistently completed. In turn, the inner layer of the column: ($\leftarrow Ln$), contains the central period of reorientation of the functional fragments of the column neutron: ($\frac{"A" (Pi / 6)'}{1/2 nykl}$), defined as "reducing", before the transition, the number is the field of the number of double units of the column volumes: ($\frac{"A" (Pi / 6)'}{(Pi / 6)}$). In particular, the degree of transition (st^n), the number is the field of the number of periods of reorientation of the column: ($\leftarrow Ln$), informatively, corresponds to the negative base:

(83) $st^n \rightarrow \ln(1.00267614) / \ln(0.99471839) = -0.5046766$ Whereas, the ratio of the arguments of the reorientation of the number and the number field, in the column ($\leftarrow Ln$), assumes only a one-sided negative limit of the number field, changing the value of the degree of transition (st^n), to the content of the quantitative (kol') and the number of the event (n^n) of a given substance, located within these limits of the central superposition:

$$(84) \quad kol' \rightarrow \ln(0.0026726) / -0.0052956 = 1118.799168 \leftrightarrow n^n \rightarrow (kol')^{-1} = 0.000893815$$

To determine the relationship between these definitions, the reduced number of the event (n^n) should be translated as the base of the reduced value of the number of the positive limit of column reorientation ($\leftarrow Ln$):

$$(85) \quad (\exp(n^n))^3 = 1.0026850 \leftrightarrow \ln(1.0026850) = 0.002681446$$

In this case, the correction of numerical values implies a more consistent order of the principle of calculation composition. For example, the cube root of the quantitative (kol') leads to the sum (sum) of all eleven nucleons of Table A of the numerical structure of nucleons within the mass numbers, column (mn): 13 – 12; sum $\rightarrow \sqrt[3]{kol'} = 10.38127538$. The content of the linear sequence of the field of the reduced nucleon ($nykl'$) in the following expression of the field of the proton number: $nykl' \rightarrow sum / 11 = 0.943752307 \leftrightarrow \sqrt[8]{nykl'} \rightarrow 0.992789678^{-1} \approx mp'(1.007262688)$.

The core of the proposed subject is that the "discharged" fusion of external and internal space under dark matter conditions resides in the content of volume units. This definition differs fundamentally from "classical" concepts of the quantum nature of spatial interactions. Thus, the proposed model provides a realistic opportunity to determine the functional external structure of the content of the volume contour of the reduced state of a flickering photon. First and foremost, this is the external gravitational background of the gravitational composition of the defined volume, located within the functional structure of the expansion process. In this case, these conditions are determined by the numbers of reduced nucleons in the composition of a unit of a given scale in Table "A" of the numerical structure of nucleons within the mass range of 13–12. To begin, it's necessary to determine the internal state of the photon's numerical structure, the "Table of Numerical Events of Nucleon Interaction." This table provides the result of the sequential difference between the periods of Table "A" of the nucleon numerical structure within the mass numbers 13–12. Thus, before you is the biblical origin of the seven known circles. It should be noted that in the table of numerical events, the interaction of nucleons, five columns (B, C, D, E, F) constitute the constant numbers of events. These columns, in turn, distribute the superposition of two fundamental functions—the proton and the neutron.

Table of numerical events of nucleon interactions

A	B	C	D	E	F	H
	"B"(Pi / 6)'	1/2 "A"	"A"(Pi / 6)'	"A"(Pi / 6)'	nykl	
← Ln	(Pi / 6)	"B"(Pi / 6)	(Pi / 6)	1/2 nykl	m / 12	← Ln'
p'(0.007722)	0.00759909	0.0039789	0.00795775	0.0041667	0.008333	p'(0.007722)
0/0077821	0.00759909	0.0039789	0.00795775	0.0041667	0.008333	0.0077821
0.0078432	0.00759909	0.0039789	0.00795775	0.0041667	0.008333	0.0078432
0.0079052	0.00759909	0.0039789	0.00795775	0.0041667	0.008333	0.0079052
0.0079682	0.00759909	0.0039789	0.00795775	0.0041667	0.008333	0.0079682
0.0080322	0.00759909	0.0039789	0.00795775	0.0041667	0.008333	0.0080322
0.0080972	0.00759909	0.0039789	0.00795775	0.0041667	0.008333	0.0080972
0.0081633	0.00759909	0.0039789	0.00795775	0.0041667	0.008333	0.0081633
0.0082305	0.00759909	0.0039789	0.00795775	0.0041667	0.008333	0.0082305
n ¹ (0.0082988)	n ² (0.00759909)	n ³ (0.0039789)	n ⁴ (0.00795775)	n ⁵ (0.0041667)	n ⁶ (0.008333)	n ⁷ (0.0082988)
sum(v ⁻¹)	sum(v ⁻¹)	sum(v ⁻¹)	sum(v ⁻¹)	sum(v ⁻¹)	sum(v ⁻¹)	sum(v ⁻¹)
0.0800427	0.07599089	0.0397887	0.07957747	0.0416667	0.0833333	0.0800427
sum ⁻¹	sum ⁻¹	sum ⁻¹	sum ⁻¹	sum ⁻¹	sum ⁻¹	sum ⁻¹
12.49333	13.1594725	25.132741	12.5663706	24	12	12.49333
exp(n ¹)	exp(n ²)	exp(n ³)	exp(n ⁴)	exp(n ⁵)	exp(n ⁶)	exp(n ⁷)
1.0083333	1.00762804	1.0039868	1.00798949	1.0041754	1.0083682	1.0083333

Here, the central column (D) defines the composition of one total event number (n⁴) – the base of one half of the sum of the reduced proton and neutron: exp(n⁴) = 1.00798949. It should be noted that the two columns: (F) and (H) refer to the value of the reduced neutrons. In this case, the content of the numerical composition of the outer column (H) is not constant. In this definition, the principle of the sequence of the double volume expansion process is presented: (2(Pi / 6)'), determined by the event number of the transition proton: (p'(0.007722)), column (H):

$$(86) \quad 2(\text{Pi} / 6)' \rightarrow (\exp(p'))^6 = 1.047422097 \leftrightarrow (\text{Pi}/6)' \rightarrow 1.047422097 / 2 = 0.523711049$$

From the ratio of the primary volume, the expansion action between: (Pi / 6) and (Pi/6)', it follows that the content of the distributed contours is related to the number of nucleons of Helium (nykl(He)):

$$(87) \quad \text{nykl(He)} \rightarrow ((\text{Pi}/6)' / (\text{Pi}/6))^3 = 1.00064425 \leftrightarrow 4\text{nykl(He)} = m_2(\text{He}^4) \rightarrow 4.002577$$

This gives a cyclic correction to the definition of the quantitative (kol') superposition (84):

(88) $\text{kol}'' \rightarrow \ln[(\exp((\text{Pi} / 6)' / (\text{Pi} / 6)))] = 0.000898184 \leftrightarrow$ (84) $\text{kol}'(0.000893815)$

This correction, for comparison, applies to the determination of the quantitative nucleon and the mass of the mirror nucleus of Oxygen to the cyclic power:

(89) $(\exp(\text{kol}'' - \text{kol}'))^8 \rightarrow 1.00034953^{-1} = \text{nykl O} \rightarrow 16(\text{nyklO}) = \text{mO}(15.99944078)$

In turn, the contents of columns (A) and (B), in contrast to columns (F) and (H), separate the layers of reduced numbers of neutron and proton events. In this definition of the state of the internal content of the general contour of a reduced unit of volume, it should be noted that the periodic orders of columns ($\leftarrow \text{Ln}$) and ($\leftarrow \text{Ln}'$) of the main table "A" of the numerical structure of nucleons within the mass numbers: 13 - 12, as already mentioned, are separated by the column reorientation period: $(\frac{1/2 \text{ "A" }}{\text{"B" (Pi / 6)}})$, after which the functional fragment of the neutron passes into the functional fragment of the proton:

$\text{fmn} (0.5013381 \rightarrow \text{fmp} (0.4973592).$

In any case, all sums (v^1) of the numerical events in the seven columns of the nucleon interaction numerical event table refer to the value of the first volume of the "Primary Volume Structure Matrix."

The details of determining the relationships between these values and the actual numbers of proton and neutron functional fragments of all known isotopes are beyond the scope of this topic.

5. Topology of justification of the nature of an expanding object:

Continuing with the topic of the analytical topology of the imaginary Higgs boson or flickering photon, we should return to the stated definition of the nature of the gravitational background in the fixed numerical structure of the contour of the represented object, specifically, the state of its expansion process, obtained from the data of the table of numerical events of nucleon interactions. In this case, this is the matrix of shifted limits of complex compositions of the superposition of the relationship between the inner and outer space of general dark matter, proposed as: "The distribution matrix of the gravitational background of the processes of compression and expansion of visible matter." In this context, the helical matrix of the gravitational background of the compression and expansion processes of visible matter defines the positive and negative values of the variable horizontal linear and perpendicular volumetric layers of the functional structure of two determining charges. In the first case, this is the periodic composition of the result of the fundamental displacement (z') of the supersymmetry of the superposition of a spatial unit of volume: (Pi/6).

The distribution matrix of the gravitational background of the processes of compression and expansion of visible matter

	$z (+/-)$	(-)	(+)	(-)	(+)	(-)	$\uparrow(+)\mathbf{z}' \rightarrow$	-6.0094E-05
						$\downarrow\mathbf{A} \rightarrow$	9.42671E-07	-6.1037E-05
				$\downarrow\mathbf{C} \rightarrow$	$\uparrow\mathbf{B} \rightarrow$	-2.2356E-08	9.65027E-07	-6.2002E-05
			$\uparrow\mathbf{D} \rightarrow$	-2.862E-11	7.41189E-10	-2.381E-08	1.01191E-06	-6.4002E-05
		$\downarrow\mathbf{E} \rightarrow$	1.38587E-12	-3.0006E-11	7.71195E-10	-2.4581E-08	1.03649E-06	-6.5039E-05
	$\downarrow\mathbf{F} \rightarrow$	-8.7218E-14	1.47309E-12	-3.1479E-11	8.02675E-10	-2.5384E-08	1.06187E-06	-6.61E-05
G	-6.151E-15	-8.1067E-14	1.55415E-12	-3.3034E-11	8.35708E-10	-2.622E-08	1.08809E-06	-6.7188E-05
H	7.917E-15	-8.8984E-14	1.64314E-12	-3.4677E-11	8.70385E-10	-2.709E-08	1.11518E-06	-6.8304E-05
	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum $\leftrightarrow e^-$
\mathbf{z}^0	1.766E-15	-2.5727E-13	6.05624E-12	-1.5782E-10	4.73372E-09	-1.7251E-07	8.20933E-06	-0.00057676

This value of the established offset is specified by the number of the reduced nucleon—a unit determined by the event number of the transition proton base ($p'(0.007722)$) of the internal column ($\leftarrow \text{Ln}$) of the table of numerical events of nucleon interactions.

As can be seen, column (A) of the specified table contains the result of the progression of the transition proton base value: $(p'(0.007722))$, to the reduced neutron base: $(n^1(0.0082988) \leftrightarrow \exp(n^1) = mn'(1.0083333))$. In turn, the sum of the numerical events of the expansion process, located in the quantum sequence of this result, the matrix of the unfolding of the turn of the gravitational background of the processes of compression and expansion of visible matter, represents the reduced value of the mass of the electron structure: $(m_e = -0.00057676)$. Further, as a result of the successive gradation of the numerical structure of the reduced electron: $(m_e = -0.00057676)$, the "open" charge $(z^0 \rightarrow 1.766E-15)$.

5.1. Topology of the nature of the object:

This concept requires clarification of the principle connecting this calculus with the fundamental data of quantum physics. Specifically, this concerns the relationship between mass and energy definitions between the resting state of established constants and the functional transformation of these values under the conditions of interaction between spatial structures of volume units. To do this, it is generally necessary to define the general concept of energy itself. In this topic, this concept refers to the background—a product determined by a function—the action of the product content of the function's composition, where the function's composition corresponds to the order of the product content limits. In the simplified concept of quantum physics, where the product limits are conventionally defined as imaginary rest energy, these data, in a certain sense, may have practical significance in terms of the realization of actual quantum interactions. However, the existing theoretical framework is unable to reconcile with practice. Frankly, the "search" for massless particles and the supposed "pure," "eternal" energy of these particles in a vacuum is sheer absurdity, verging on the fiction of academic dreamers. This particularly applies to the much-talked-about Higgs boson. This will be discussed further in this content. So, based on fundamental physical data, the electron's rest energy is defined as: $\text{MeV} = 0.51099895$. From a topological perspective, it represents a spatial unit of volume. More precisely, for a detailed topological analysis, this value can be represented in several effective definitions. As you understand, this is not a finite value.

▪ Firstly, this is the first reduced base: (Basis 1), units of spatial (primary) volume: $(\text{Basis } 1' = 0.51099895)$, of the matrix "Primary Volume Structure Matrix". Consequently, the relic projection of the reduced mass is determined: (W_m) , as the numerical structure of the composition of the content of a given energy background:

$$(90) \quad {}^1V' \rightarrow ((\text{Pi}(\text{Basis } 1')^3) / 6) = 0.0698648 \leftrightarrow W_m \rightarrow ({}^1V')^{-1} = 14.313352$$

Furthermore, the nucleon $(\text{nykl}(m))$ —the unit of mass, the unit of charge, and the displacement of supersymmetry over spatial units of volume—leads to a superposition of the central interaction of the fundamental functions of the proton and neutron within mirror-image nuclei. In this case, the nature of these functional interactions is as follows:

$$(91) \quad \text{nykl}(W_m) \rightarrow W_m / 14 = 1.0223823 \leftrightarrow {}^{16}\sqrt{\text{nykl}(W_m)} \rightarrow (mn / mp) = 1.001384425$$

$$(92) \quad \text{nykl}(W_m) \rightarrow W_m / 14 = 1.0223823 \leftrightarrow {}^{32}\sqrt{\text{nykl}(W_m)} \rightarrow (mn' / mp') = 1.00069197^{-1} \leftrightarrow 0.99930851$$

In the case of position (91), the sixteenth root of the linear sequence of the order of interaction of the compression and expansion limits of the superposition of the ratios of the static neutron: $(mn = 1.008665012)$ and the proton: $(mp = 1.00727647)$ is presented. These conditions apply to any of the separated column (E'), "Matrix of perpendicular orders of natural numbers." Whereas, in the case of the zero, central superposition of the entire composition of natural numbers of this matrix, twice the thirty-second power allows us to determine a "deeper" compression limit of the interaction of the basic functions of the proton and neutron, represented by the internal and external space of matter. Under these interaction conditions, the desired and

"fashionable" resonance does not and cannot exist, since the values of external, visible space are represented by a number, while the values of invisible space are represented, as already stated, by its field. Thus, position (92) determines not a number, but the field of the central proton of the mirror nuclei. Consequently, the thirty-second power will be negative. This is due to the fact that, given the natural displacement of the projections of internal and external space, determined by the constant pi, the subsequent expansion of these interactions takes on a spiral form. In this case, the constant pi itself is not constant—it's reduced, relative to the base shift, by dividing supersymmetry into the neutron function content and the proton function content. This determines the precise value of the calculated result. For example, the open volume conditions of Phase 1 (Phase 1), in the "Primary Volume Structure Matrix," provide the second base of the reduced pi ($\ln(\text{Pi}')$), which relates this value to the real neutron number (mn') of the mirror nucleus of helium (${}^2\text{He}^4$):

$$(93) \text{ Phase 1} \rightarrow (\text{Basis } 1' = 0.51099895)^3 \rightarrow \ln(\text{Pi}') = 0133432008$$

In this case, the given second base of Pi (Pi') transforms the following value of given Pi (Pi''):

$$(94) \text{ Pi}'' \rightarrow \exp(\exp(\text{Phase 1})) = 3.13535864$$

$$(95) \text{ mn}'({}^2\text{He}^4) \rightarrow \text{Pi} / \text{Pi}'' = 1.00198829$$

After which, knowing the actual number of protons of mirror nuclei, and knowing the specific actual number of neutrons of the mirror nucleus of Helium (${}^2\text{He}^4$), its mass ($m {}^2\text{He}^4$) is determined:

$$(96) m {}^2\text{He}^4 \rightarrow 2\text{mn}' + 2\text{mp}'(0.99930851) = 4.0025936$$

▪ Secondly, the ratio of the presented energy background: ($E(m_e)$), of the first reduced base: ($\text{Basis } 1' = 0.51099895$), to the center of the static volume: ($\text{Pi}/6$), represents the first phase of expansion, in the form of two "open" volumes, of the reduced static neutron (mn^3):

$$(97) \text{ mn}^3 \rightarrow (\text{Pi}/6) / 0.51099895 \rightarrow \sqrt[3]{1.0246572} = 1.0081524$$

▪ *Explanation of the subject*

Here, the definition of "open" volume represents a cubic power. In this case, the given neutron value refers to the base number of the "open" volume. In particular, for further clarification of linear definitions in the volume structure, the paired meaning of the ratio of a number and a number field in the square structure is used. For example: (A) $n / n^{-1} = n^2$

In the conditions of the sum of a number and a number field, the central value of the limits of linear "compression" and "expansion" in a binary structure is determined.

$$\text{For example: (B) } n + n^{-1} = 2.000593347 / 2 = 1.000296674$$

$$\text{In this case, the maximum expansion limit is: (C) } 1.000296674^{11} = 1.835831343$$

$$\text{Thus, the next square of this limit goes into a ternary structure: (D) } 1.835831343^2 \rightarrow 3.37027672$$

$$\text{Difference of linear limit of binary structure: (E) } 2 - 1.835831343 = 0.164168657$$

$$\text{This leads to the value of the third base of the primary volume structure (Pi/6)'. In turn, this value is the number field (n): (F) } n \rightarrow (0.164168657)^{11} = 6.091324303$$

Thus, the number of nucleon (nykl), which determines the limit of displacement of the six-digit structure, will be the following value of the reduced number of the proton:

$$(G) \text{nykl} \rightarrow 6.091324303 / 6 = 1.015220717 \leftrightarrow \sqrt[4]{1.015220717} = {}_1mp(1.007581618)$$

This is the result of the expansion of the reduced volume structure. Then, the result of compression (${}_1\Sigma$) can be the following limit: $(H) {}^1\Sigma \rightarrow \sqrt[8]{1.000296674} = 1.000037079$

Thus, the linear limits of compression and expansion in a binary structure are defined. Naturally, the degree of transition ($st^n = 16384.17135$) is a quantitative periodic value of this content. Its exponent has its own base legend, as does each fixed period between the established limits of a given linear structure. The encoding of these complex definitions, in very approximate values, is contained in the transition periods between the limits of the linear structures of real physical quantities. For example, the base of the transition degree (st^n) between the compression and expansion limits of the six-valued structure determines, by the nucleon number ($nykl^n$), the further value of the number or number field for the superposition conditions (Σ) of these limits in the four-valued linear structure of the reduced unit volume. This leads to the proton number field: ${}_1mp(1.007581618)$, the displacement limit of the six-valued structure:

$$(I) \Sigma(\ln(st^n)) \rightarrow 9.704070986 \rightarrow nykl^n(9.704070986 / 10) \rightarrow 0.970407099 \rightarrow \sqrt[4]{nykl^n} \rightarrow {}_2mp(0.992518227)^{-1} = 1.007538172$$

Thus, the mirror projection of the degree minus one, number – number field, is disrupted as a result of the shift in the underlying superposition. In this case, the degree of transition (${}_1st^n$) will be as follows:

$$(J) ({}_1st^n) \rightarrow \ln({}_1mp) / \ln({}_2mp) = -1.005741808$$

As a limit of a negative base, this definition leads to a linear relationship between two constants (e^{-1}) and the second base (${}_2Pi'$):

$$(K) \exp({}_1st^n) \rightarrow e^{-1}(0.365773201) \rightarrow (e^{-1})^2 \rightarrow {}_2Pi' = 0.133790034 \leftrightarrow \exp(\exp({}_2Pi) = Pi'(3.13661908)$$

In turn, the ratio – the expansion of the constants: Pi and Pi' , between themselves, is determined by the general five-digit degree of superposition (Σ^1) of the reduced nucleon of Hydrogen ($nykl(H^1)$):

$$(L) \text{nykl}(H^1) \rightarrow (Pi / Pi')^5 \rightarrow 1.00792929$$

Therefore, the result of the compression limit, denoted by the position (H) , of this definition is a helical element of the linear sequence between the established compression and expansion limits in the binary system of the structure of a unit volume. Here, this value defines the nucleon ($nyklO$) – the unit charge of oxygen:

$$(M) \text{nykl}O \rightarrow (H)^{-1} = 0.999962922 \leftrightarrow m({}_8O^{16}) \rightarrow 16(\text{nykl}O) = 15.99940676$$

In addition to the explanation provided, the following should be clarified. The author deliberately avoids using the physical symbol for limits (ψ), preferring the mathematical (Σ) definition for quantum computations. This follows from the fact that the author, firstly, utilizes the discrete mathematics of fundamental physical quantities within the context of quantum volume structures. Secondly, this naturally excludes the wave and electrical nature of these definitions. Thus, the author provides an expandable object in which the interactions of units of the limits of compression and expansion of quantum volumes are primarily separated structures, the superpositions of which relate to opposite values of the external and internal space of the general dark matter. In this case, the functional interaction of the presented units of volume determines only the structure of phase transitions of the mass compositions of the object under study. Only after the value of physical mass is formed, and based on this, does the discrete structure transform into the variable value of wave interactions of already known light, electromagnetic, and other physical concepts. Indeed, from the mathematical conditions of negative bases, this value of the established limit has no root expression. The

determined limit is subject only to the opposite action of the degree of expansion (an increase in the value of the number). However, each negative base has a degree of freedom in the form of a projection of any negative degree, in particular, a mirror projection of minus one, which determines a relic connection with the sequence of subsequent transformed limits of compression and expansion of the studied matter structures. For example, the shifted mirror projection of the superposition with the transition degree ($1st^n$) in the following position:

$$(N) \ 1st^n \rightarrow \ln({}_1mp) / \ln({}_2mp) = -1.005741808$$

Which can be represented as a state of the compression limit ($\downarrow\Sigma$) between one and minus one, with the subsequent definition of a linear superposition of the mirror values of the positive and negative bases of the numerical events ($n^{(+/-)}$):

$$(O) \ \downarrow\Sigma \rightarrow (1st^n + 1) \rightarrow n^- = -0.005741808^2 \leftarrow n^{(+/-)} \rightarrow \sqrt{0.000032968} \rightarrow n^+ = 0.005741808$$

In this case, the linear expansion information ($\uparrow\Sigma$) leads to the content of a positive displacement per unit volume ($(Pi/6)'$):

$$(P) \ \uparrow\Sigma \rightarrow (Pi/6)' \rightarrow {}^{16}\sqrt{n^+} = 0.524663782$$

Therefore, this definition can be used as a linear—an internal structural connection between background (energy) transformative interactions. For example, the presented transformation of position (O) can be indirectly compared with the data at position ninety-seven (97) of the main text, which discusses the rest energy of an electron:

$$(Q) \ (Pi/6)' / (Pi/6) \rightarrow 1.002034012^4 = 1.008160904 \leftrightarrow (97) = 1.0081524$$

To conclude, let's clarify the subject. The given value of the negative base position (J) of this clarification defines its binary limits related to the supersymmetry of the central definition of the relationship between the inner and outer space of a common material. Here, in particular, we are talking about the proton number of all mirror nuclei, which is the field of the ratio of the fundamental masses of the neutron and proton (mp'):

$$(R) \ (N) \rightarrow n^- + 1 \rightarrow \exp(\exp(\exp(-2.005741808))) = Pi'(3.139406606)$$

$$(S) \ mp' \rightarrow Pi' / Pi = 0.999304159 \leftrightarrow (92) \leftrightarrow (96)$$

$$(T) \ \sqrt{(mn(1.008665012) / mp(1,00727647))} = 1.000689018^{-1} \rightarrow mp' = 0.999311456$$

In this case, the static meaning of the quantities and the functional definition of these values must have a similar distinctive orientation of these definitions.

Continuing with the topic: “**5.1. Topology of the nature of the object**”, from the position:

$$(97) \ mn^3 \rightarrow (Pi/6) / 0.51099895 \rightarrow \sqrt[3]{1.0246572} = 1.0081524$$

What constitutes the first phase of expansion, in the form of two "open" volumes, is the reduced static neutron: ($mn^3 = 1.0081524$). The square of this expansion—the ratio of two volume constants relative to the electron energy—results in two mirror volumes, differing in the content of functional structures, the superposition of which is the helium nucleon (nykl (He)):

$$(98) \ \frac{1}{2}((Pi/6) / 0.51099895)^2 \rightarrow \sqrt{(0.5249612 / (Pi/6))} \rightarrow nykl(He) = 1.0006499 \leftrightarrow m({}_2He^4) \rightarrow 4nykl = 4.0025996$$

This unites the equality of positions (95), (96), and (98), thereby defining the sole source of energy for the expansion process and functional separation, within the interaction, by dividing discrete values of units of

internal volume relative to one another. As can be seen, in one case, position (95) determines the number of the helium neutron (${}^4_2\text{He}$), while in the other, position (98) determines its nucleon. Thus, as a result of the expansion energy, certain functional "communications" arise, distributing the composite values of known mass formations due to the product of shifted supersymmetries of the compression limits of superpositions of reduced units of volume. It's worth noting, as a rule, that the level of these interactions is determined by the second base of pi. This is explained by the fact that this level is bound by the limits of the linear structure that unites the value of the unit field of the constant number base (e) with the linear structure of the second base of pi (positions (9) and (12) of this test:

$$(99) \ln(\ln(\text{Pi})) \rightarrow \sqrt{0.135168702} \leftrightarrow 'e^{-1} \rightarrow \ln(2.719956315) \rightarrow \text{mn}({}_8\text{O}^{16}) = 1.000615819$$

Thus, the fundamental primordial superposition of matter belongs to genetics. In turn, the significance of cosmology, particularly the heliocentrism of the solar system, confirms this feature, in that organic matter resides within this formation. In this case, the principle of genetic superposition, found in the structure of helium, belongs to three fundamental elements: hydrogen, oxygen, and nitrogen. Here, once again, it is worth reminding respected physicists that their subject has no continuation in the search for a common paradigm of the physical world without recognizing the divine origin of global consciousness for their ambitions for primacy. The consistency of the fundamental metric of consciousness, as a global combinatorics of material processes under the conditions of the functional interaction of internal and external space, belongs to the structure of the unit. It is precisely this unit that constitutes the material central dividing value between visible and invisible space. Consequently, based on the conditions of fundamental constants, in particular the structure of pi, and the basic composition of natural numbers, according to elementary arithmetic operations, the structure of the unit can change its limiting state positively or negatively, while maintaining its value. For example, the basis of the Hydrogen nucleon (H^1), equal to its charge, as the limit of the number of events ('n) of one half of the quantitative (kolH^1), determining the interaction of the limits of the reduced charge ($z^{(+/-)}$), the gravitational background formed by the conditions of negative and positive content, the interactions of the quantum compositions of the periods of compression and expansion of the limits (G) and (H), "The matrix of the unfolding of the turn of the gravitational background of the processes of compression and expansion of visible matter":

$$(100) \text{kolH}^1 \rightarrow \ln(\text{nykl H}^1) \rightarrow \ln(1.00794) \rightarrow 0.007908644^{-1} = 126.4439253$$

First of all, the mirror image of these spatial projections is determined by their difference:

$$(101) G(-6.151\text{E}-15) - H(7.917\text{E}-15) = 1.40686\text{E}-14 \leftrightarrow H(7.917\text{E}-15) - G(-6.151\text{E}-15) = -1,4069\text{E}-14$$

Further, the sum and difference of these definitions in the conditions of functional interactions of phase field mirror projections: $((A+B)/A)^{-1} \leftrightarrow ((A+B)/B)^{-1}$, in the form of limits of influence of the general space that forms the composition of the structure of the reduced charge: ($z^{(+/-)}$), leads to the following content. In the process of expansion ($\uparrow\Sigma$):

$$(101) \uparrow\Sigma. \rightarrow ((G - H)/H)^{-1} = 0.5 \leftrightarrow ((G - H)/G)^{-1} = -0.5$$

During compression ($\downarrow\Sigma$):

$$(102) \downarrow\Sigma. \rightarrow ((G - H) \times H)^{-1} = 2.5262\text{E}+27 \leftrightarrow ((G - H) \times G)^{-1} = -2.5262\text{E}+27$$

Thus, only the negative compression limit is determined. In the case of a positive limit, the same basis of one-half the quantitative nucleon of Hydrogen (H^1) follows:

$$(103) \frac{1}{2}(\text{kolH}^1) \rightarrow \ln(((G - H) \times H)^{-1}) = 63.09651383 \leftrightarrow \text{kolH}^1 = 126.1930277$$

Here, the shift in the mirror image of the opposite spatial limits can be represented relative to the hundredth position (100) of the static expression of the quantitative structure of the charge of Hydrogen:

$$(104) \quad (100) - (103) \rightarrow 126.4439253 - 63.09651383 = 63.34741147$$

The principle of successive expansion - the ratio of the shifted compositions of the positive base limit determines the degree of freedom - the square root of one half of the sum of the static neutron: ($mn = 1.008665012$), to the static proton: ($mp + 1.00727647$):

$$(105) \quad 63.34741147 / 63.09651383 = 1.003976411^2 \leftrightarrow 2(1.007968633) \rightarrow (mp + mn)$$

In this case, the expansion ($\uparrow\Sigma$) of hydrogen (H^1) occurs due to the reduction of its charge within the limits between the opposite values of the phase states of position (101), where, as a result of the phase limits, the functional distribution of these limits is determined.

Thus, for example, for the case of the imaginary Higgs boson mass determined by position (82) from section "3. Specific topology of the subject": (82) $m(H^0) \rightarrow (n^s)^{-1} = 125.4993305$. Following the data of the table of numerical events of nucleon interactions, the functional structure of such a boson is also subject to the definition of its nucleon number ($nykl H^0$):

$$(106) \quad nykl H^0 \rightarrow 125.4993305 / 125 = 1.003994688$$

This is the data for column (C), phase (A), of the table of numerical events of nucleon interactions. In this case, without charge mass, the value of the displacement product state, in the unit structure, is determined within the range of mass numbers: $126 - 125 = 1$. For the proposed case, this fractional part of the mass is defined as the functional fragment of the proton (fmp) or neutron (fmn). Specifically, it is the functional fragment of the reduced proton number (fmp'):

$$(107) \quad fmp' \rightarrow 125.4993305 - 125 = 4993305$$

Thus, knowing the nucleon, one can establish the number of the functional fragment of the reduced number of neutrons:

$$(108) \quad fmn' \rightarrow nykl H^0 - fmp = 0.50465871$$

In the case of determining the displacement of the superposition by the arguments of the proton and neutron in the structure of the unit itself, without the intervention of the nucleon number, the dynamics of the functional interaction of the proton and neutron fragments will be cyclical, "Table 1."

Table1.

Φ^A	Φ^B	$\Phi^B - \Phi^A$	$m(\Phi^A/125^{-1})$	$m(\Phi^A/125^{-1})$
0.499335987	0.500664013	0.001328027	62.58300168	62.41699832
0.499335987	0.500664013	0.001328027	62.58300168	62.41699832

In this case, of the continuous function, Table 1, the arguments of the phase interactions become the values of the reduced masses.

The determined structure "folds" with the subsequent separation of the product of its difference and becomes static relative to its content (Table 1). When the separation of functional fragments occurs relative to the nucleon number, the phase interaction takes on the dynamic nature of processes: compression, expansion, reorientation of functional transition processes, followed by the formation of mass and charge structures. Specifically, this should be demonstrated. For the conditions for the distribution of proton and neutron functional fragment values in the unit structure (Table 1), this will be as follows:

$$(109) \quad fmn'' \rightarrow (1 - fmp') = 0.50066401$$

Next, the functional interaction of phases (Φ^A) and (Φ^B), relative to the proton and neutron fragments, with subsequent determination of the degree of freedom (st^{sv}):

$$(110) \quad \Phi^A \rightarrow ((fmp' + fmn'') / fmp')^{-1} = 0.499335987$$

$$(111) \quad \Phi^B \rightarrow ((fmp' + fmn'') / fmn'')^{-1} = 0.50066401$$

$$(112) \quad st^{sv} \rightarrow \Phi^B - \Phi^A = 0.001328027$$

Here, the value of masses in the composition of the mass number (125) will be distributed as follows:

$$(113) \quad m(fmp') \rightarrow \Phi^A / 125^{-1} = 62.4169983$$

$$(114) \quad m(fmn'') \rightarrow \Phi^B / 125^{-1} = 62.58300168$$

As can be seen, the Higgs conditions are satisfied for the imaginary mass without charge content, since the further interaction of these represented mass numbers, even during the expansion process, will remain unchanged. In this case, the difference between these definitions is the reduced value of the third base (Basis 3'), "Primary Volume Structure Matrix":

$$(115) \quad \text{Basis } 3' \rightarrow m(fmn'') - m(fmp') = 0.1660034$$

This value is the event number ('n) of the six approximate nucleons (nykl) of position (106):

$$(116) \quad 'n \rightarrow (0.1660034)^{-1} \rightarrow 6.0239745 / 6 = \text{nykl}(1.003995754)$$

5.2. Topology of the formation of mass values of an object:

In the case defined by the nucleon, that is, the unit of charge, the interaction of functional phase values takes on the dynamic content of mass definitions. In particular, this concerns the futile attempts to synthesize new superheavy isotopes, which, as classical physicists believe, belong to the general mass of the Universe. As is well known, the cascade of such "discoveries" only leads to enormous material expenditures on these unfounded studies of so-called experimental physics. It is surprising that not a single existing official theory refutes these senseless endeavors, but only clumsily attempts to somehow justify this absurdity. It must be the same old money... But, based on the premise that all human activity has its own meaning, the same scientific data obtained from experimental physics also have their own undeniable meaning, the proof of which is the objective truth of the shared consciousness's response to the meaning of its existence in the world around us. The author invites the reader to jointly analyze these data, obtained through the synthesis of new isotopes, in the following interpretation. For example, for the same mass of the imaginary Higgs boson, taking into account its nucleon number, position (106).

As can be seen, the content of the proposed Table 2 begins with a non-existent isotope, the imaginary mass of the Higgs boson, Samarium (${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$). An important element for all stable and unstable masses is the number of the degree of maximum "approximation" of the values of the proton and neutron within the nucleon. In this case, these are the values of the number and the number field, that is, the numerical content of the isotopic mass of visible and invisible matter. In this version, the author returns the reader to the functional paradigm – the cause of the nucleon expansion process – the unit charge of Hydrogen (H^1), for stable nuclei of the periodic table: ([The mathematical table of stable chemical symbols, \(page 35\)](#)), (2. General topology of the subject, read between positions (24-25), see "Table 2.").

Table 2.

N	$\downarrow \Sigma$ (fmp)	$\uparrow \Sigma$ (fnn)	st^{sv}	m(fmp)	m(fnn)	mp'	mn'
→	${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$	${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$	fnn - fmp	${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$	${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$	${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$	${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$
1	0.49933599	0.50465871	0.00532273	62.4169983	63.082339	1.00672578	1.00130697
2	0.497349226	0.50664547	0.00929625	62.1686532	63.330684	1.00272021	1.00524896
3	0.49537037	0.50862433	0.01325396	61.9212962	63.578041	0.99873058	1.00917526
4	0.493399387	0.51059531	0.01719593	61.6749234	63.824414	0.99475683	0.99725647
→	${}_{61}\text{Pm}^{125}$	${}_{61}\text{Pm}^{125}$	${}_{61}\text{Pm}^{125}$	${}_{61}\text{Pm}^{125}$	${}_{61}\text{Pm}^{125}$	${}_{61}\text{Pm}^{125}$	${}_{61}\text{Pm}^{125}$
5	0.491436247	0.51255845	0.02112221	61.4295308	64.069807	1.00704149	1.00109073
6	0.489480917	0.51451378	0.02503287	61.1851147	64.314223	1.00303467	1.00490973
7	0.487533368	0.51646133	0.02892796	60.941671	64.557667	0.99904379	1.00871354
8	0.485593567	0.51840113	0.03280757	60.6991959	64.800142	0.99506879	0.99692526
→	${}_{60}\text{Nd}^{125}$	${}_{60}\text{Nd}^{125}$	${}_{60}\text{Nd}^{125}$	${}_{60}\text{Nd}^{125}$	${}_{60}\text{Nd}^{125}$	${}_{60}\text{Nd}^{125}$	${}_{60}\text{Nd}^{125}$
9	0.483661485	0.52033322	0.03667173	60.4576856	65.041652	1.00762809	1.00064080
10	0.481737089	0.52225761	0.04052052	60.2171362	65.282201	1.00361894	1.00434156
11	0.479820351	0.52417435	0.04435400	59.9775439	65.521794	0.99962573	1.00802759
12	0.477911239	0.52608346	0.04817222	59.7389049	65.760433	0.99564841	0.99637019
→	${}_{59}\text{Pr}^{125}$	${}_{59}\text{Pr}^{125}$	${}_{59}\text{Pr}^{125}$	${}_{59}\text{Pr}^{125}$	${}_{59}\text{Pr}^{125}$	${}_{59}\text{Pr}^{125}$	${}_{59}\text{Pr}^{125}$
13	0.476009723	0.52798498	0.05197525	59.5012154	65.998122	1.00849518	0.99997155
14	0.474115773	0.52987893	0.05576315	59.2644716	66.234866	1.00448257	1.00355857
15	0.472229358	0.53176534	0.05953598	59.0286698	66.470668	1.00048593	1.00713133
16	0.470350449	0.53364425	0.06329380	58.7938061	66.705531	0.99650519	0.99560495
→	${}_{58}\text{Ce}^{125}$	${}_{58}\text{Ce}^{125}$	${}_{58}\text{Ce}^{125}$	${}_{58}\text{Ce}^{125}$	${}_{58}\text{Ce}^{125}$	${}_{58}\text{Ce}^{125}$	${}_{58}\text{Ce}^{125}$
17	0.468479016	0.53551568	0.06703667	58.559877	66.93946	1.00965305	0.99909643
18	0.466615029	0.53737967	0.07076464	58.3268786	67.172459	1.00563584	1.00257401
19	0.464758458	0.53923624	0.07447778	58.0948073	67.40453	1.00163461	1.00603776
20	0.462909275	0.54108543	0.07817615	57.8636593	67.635678	0.99764930	1.00948773
→	${}_{57}\text{La}^{125}$	${}_{57}\text{La}^{125}$	${}_{57}\text{La}^{125}$	${}_{57}\text{La}^{125}$	${}_{57}\text{La}^{125}$	${}_{57}\text{La}^{125}$	${}_{57}\text{La}^{125}$
21	0.461067449	0.54292725	0.08185980	57.6334311	67.865906	1.01111283	0.99802804
22	0.459232951	0.54476175	0.08552880	57.4041188	68.095219	1.00708980	1.00140027
23	0.457405752	0.54658895	0.08918320	57.175719	68.323619	1.00308279	1.00475910
24	0.455585823	0.54840888	0.09282305	56.9482279	68.55111	0.99909172	1.00810455
25	0.453773136	0.55022156	0.09644843	56.721642	68.777696	0.99511653	0.99677820
→	${}_{56}\text{Ba}^{125}$	${}_{56}\text{Ba}^{125}$	${}_{56}\text{Ba}^{125}$	${}_{56}\text{Ba}^{125}$	${}_{56}\text{Ba}^{125}$	${}_{56}\text{Ba}^{125}$	${}_{56}\text{Ba}^{125}$
26	0.45196766	0.55202704	0.10005938	56.4959576	69.00338	1.00885639	1.00004898
27	0.450169369	0.55382533	0.10365596	56.2711711	69.228166	1.00484234	1.00330676
28	0.448378232	0.55561647	0.10723824	56.047279	69.452058	1.00084427	1.00655157
29	0.446594222	0.55740048	0.11080626	55.8242778	69.67506	0.99686210	0.99535800
30	0.444817311	0.55917739	0.11436008	55.6021638	69.897174	0.99289578	0.99853105
→	${}_{55}\text{Cs}^{125}$	${}_{55}\text{Cs}^{125}$	${}_{55}\text{Cs}^{125}$	${}_{55}\text{Cs}^{125}$	${}_{55}\text{Cs}^{125}$	${}_{55}\text{Cs}^{125}$	${}_{55}\text{Cs}^{125}$
31	0.443047469	0.56094723	0.11789976	55.3809336	70.118404	1.00692607	1.00169148
32	0.441284669	0.56271003	0.12142536	55.1605836	70.338754	1.00291970	1.00483934
33	0.439528883	0.56446582	0.12493693	54.9411104	70.558227	0.99892928	1.00797467
34	0.437780083	0.56621462	0.12843453	54.7225104	70.776827	0.99495473	0.99685672
→	${}_{54}\text{Xe}^{125}$	${}_{54}\text{Xe}^{125}$	${}_{54}\text{Xe}^{125}$	${}_{54}\text{Xe}^{125}$	${}_{54}\text{Xe}^{125}$	${}_{54}\text{Xe}^{125}$	${}_{54}\text{Xe}^{125}$
35	0.436038241	0.56795646	0.13191822	54.5047801	70.994557	1.00934778	0.99992334
36	0.43430333	0.56969137	0.13538804	54.2879162	71.211421	1.00533178	1.00297776
37	0.432575321	0.57141938	0.13884406	54.0719151	71.427422	1.00133176	1.00602003
38	0.430854188	0.57314051	0.14228632	53.8567735	71.642564	0.99734766	0.99503561
39	0.429139903	0.57485480	0.14571489	53.6424878	71.85685	0.99337940	0.99801180
→	${}_{53}\text{I}^{125}$	${}_{53}\text{I}^{125}$	${}_{53}\text{I}^{125}$	${}_{53}\text{I}^{125}$	${}_{53}\text{I}^{125}$	${}_{53}\text{I}^{125}$	${}_{53}\text{I}^{125}$
40	0.427432438	0.57656226	0.14912982	53.4290548	72.070283	1.00809537	1.00097615
41	0.425731767	0.57826293	0.15253117	53.2164709	72.282867	1.00408436	1.00392870
42	0.424037863	0.57995684	0.15591897	53.0047329	72.494605	1.00008930	1.00686951
43	0.422350699	0.58164400	0.15929330	52.7938374	72.7055	0.99611014	0.99596576
→	${}_{52}\text{Te}^{125}$	${}_{52}\text{Te}^{125}$	${}_{52}\text{Te}^{125}$	${}_{52}\text{Te}^{125}$	${}_{52}\text{Te}^{125}$	${}_{52}\text{Te}^{125}$	${}_{52}\text{Te}^{125}$
44	0.420670248	0.58332445	0.16265420	52.583781	72.915557	1.01122656	0.99884324
45	0.418996482	0.58499822	0.16600174	52.3745603	73.124777	1.00720308	1.00170928
46	0.417329377	0.58666532	0.16933595	52.1661721	73.333165	1.00319562	1.00456391
47	0.415668904	0.58832580	0.17265689	51.958613	73.540724	0.99920410	1.00740718
48	0.414015038	0.58997966	0.17596462	51.7518798	73.747458	0.99522846	0.99658727
→	${}_{51}\text{Sb}^{125}$	${}_{51}\text{Sb}^{125}$	${}_{51}\text{Sb}^{125}$	${}_{51}\text{Sb}^{125}$	${}_{51}\text{Sb}^{125}$	${}_{51}\text{Sb}^{125}$	${}_{51}\text{Sb}^{125}$

49	0.412367753	0.59162695	0.17925919	51.5459691	73.953368	1.01070528	0.99936984
50	0.410727022	0.59326768	0.18254066	51.3408777	74.15846	1.00668388	1.00214135
51	0.409092818	0.59490188	0.18580906	51.1366023	74.362735	1.00267848	1.00490183
52	0.407465118	0.59652958	0.18906446	50.9331397	74.566198	0.99868901	0.99421597
53	0.405843893	0.59815081	0.19230691	50.7304866	74.768851	0.99471542	0.99691801
→	${}_{50}\text{Sn}^{125}$						
54	0.404229119	0.59976558	0.19553646	50.5286399	74.970698	1.01057280	0.99960930
55	0.40262077	0.60137393	0.19875316	50.3275962	75.171741	1.00655192	1.00228988
56	0.40101882	0.60297588	0.20195706	50.1273525	75.371985	1.00254705	1.00495980
57	0.399423244	0.60457146	0.20514821	49.9279055	75.571432	0.99855811	0.99436095
58	0.397834016	0.60616068	0.20832667	49.729252	75.770085	0.99458504	0.99697481
59	0.396251112	0.60774359	0.21149248	49.531389	75.967949	0.99062778	0.99957827
N	$\downarrow\Sigma$ (fmp)	$\uparrow\Sigma$ (fmp)	st^{sv}	m (fmp)	m (fmn)	mp'	mn'
→	${}_{42}\text{Mo}^{125}$						
97	0.340546582	0.66344812	0.32290154	42.5683228	82.931015	1.01353149	0.99916885
98	0.339191613	0.66480309	0.32561147	42.3989517	83.100386	1.00949885	1.00120947
99	0.337842036	0.66615266	0.32831063	42.2302545	83.269083	1.00548225	1.00324196
100	0.336497828	0.66749687	0.33099904	42.0622285	83.437109	1.00148163	1.00526637
101	0.335158968	0.66883573	0.33367676	41.8948711	83.604466	0.99749693	1.00728273
N	$\downarrow\Sigma$ (fmp)	$\uparrow\Sigma$ (fmp)	st^{sv}	m (fmp)	m (fmn)	mp'	mn'

Here, we are talking about the oxygen metric. While the returned carbon metric of Dalton separates genetics from physics. Thus, this result was addressed to the genetic nature contained in the structure of Helium - the third element in the composition of mirror nuclei, after Oxygen and Nitrogen, which divided the Hydrogen nucleon in the process of reducing its charge to the maximum limit of its compression for relatively stable nuclei, equal to the fragment, the corresponding displacement: ($z = 0.5039889$). Then, in the specific case, the established many of events, combined into the so-called Higgs boson mass (nykl H⁰), defined as the content of the structure of the Hydrogen nucleon, and represented by position (106), corresponds to this definition, in the sense that the square root of this value is equal to the neutron (mn) of the mirror nucleus of Helium (2He⁴):

$$(117) \quad mn({}_2\text{He}^4) \rightarrow \sqrt{\text{nykl H}^0} = 1.001995353 \leftrightarrow m({}_2\text{He}^4) \rightarrow 2mn + 2mp(0.999304647) = 4.0026$$

Then, the chronology of the charge number decline: ($z+/- = \text{fmp}$), the composition of these isobars, contained in Table 2, represents an analytical countdown, from the expansion limit ($\uparrow\Sigma \rightarrow {}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$), to the compression limit ($\downarrow\Sigma \rightarrow {}_{50}\text{Sn}^{125}$). It should be noted that these compositions of the limits of compression and expansion, containing certain values of their charges, are in different definitions of number and number field relative to the periods of their state. This suggests that the same charge, of the same mass, can be in different phase projections of visible and invisible matter. Here, we should turn to the history of the theoretical determination of the numerical combinations of the required number of protons and neutrons for the possible determination of the conditions for the formation of a stable mass. As is well known, this is a weight and isotopic metric. Naturally, the proposed material cannot discuss Eugene Wigner's "magic" nucleon numbers. This largely relates, in part, to the experimental work of Maria Goeppert Mayer in 1948, confirming the existence of closed nuclear shells. The concept of spin-orbit interaction is absent from the topology of discrete definitions of "closed" spatial structures of units of volume. This is because the author does not use the classical model of the atom. The meaning of the causes and conditions of the functional interaction of phase numerical structures he defines is primarily the different compositions of periodic orders of natural numbers, the sequence of which is always in opposite expression. Consequently, comparative data of these orders are characterized by corresponding arithmetic operations leading to one result or another.

For example, introducing a number to a cubic power defines the state of an unclosed, open volume. In quantum terms, this is the state of radioactivity of a nuclide. In volumetric terms, this is the first phase of the materialization of space. Furthermore, the action of multiplication is primarily the "compression" of the argu-

ment by a number, leading to the "center" of the product. For the definition of the unit of volume, the center of its space is the constant pi. This relates to the second, centering phase of the primary volume structure (Pi/6). Thus, the base number undergoes two phases before forming its volume, through the division—expansion—of the reduced "center" by six. Where the number six is the outer closed loop of the "expansion," the completed product—"compression"—of the linear and cubic powers. In turn, the sum of these arguments leads to the number five—the center of the "Matrix of Perpendicular Orders of Natural Numbers." Thus, an analysis of the compositions of stable and unstable, possible and impossible, isobar mass definitions is presented in Table 2. The first is Samarium. As is known, the smallest mass of its isotope (${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{128}$) was discovered recently, in 2025. According to the proposed table, the theoretical possibility of the existence of the isotope Samarium (${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$) assumes a diagonal combination of periods: (1 – 4), where ($mn' = 1.00130697$), ($mp' = 0.99475683$). For example, in this case, the mass value and the number of nucleons change:

$$(118) \quad m'({}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}) \rightarrow (62mp' + 63mn') = 124.7572626 \leftrightarrow nykl \rightarrow m' / 125 = 0.998058101$$

In this case, the represented nucleon is the field of the neutron of the mirror nucleus of Helium (${}_{2}\text{He}^4$):

$$(119) \quad mn({}_{2}\text{He}^4) \rightarrow nykl^{-1} = 1.001945678$$

These conditions relate to the isotopic metric for determining the content of the main mass composition. Perhaps, here, we should congratulate mainstream physics on an important factual discovery. Its excessive insistence on experimental science has led to unexpected results. Data obtained from fragmenting charges by nuclear "bombardments" of appropriate targets fully confirms the relationship between visible and invisible matter. Thus, all data obtained in this way pertain to invisible, dark matter. There remains only one option: send an observer into dark matter. Ahead of these fantastical developments, it's worth noting that in the nature of matter consciousness, this interaction between its visible and invisible spaces is already factual. This is confirmed by the well-known equivalent of the energy expended on the presence of a short-lived ghost, one or another unexpectedly emerging isotope. For comparison, the actual nucleon number of Samarium, determined by its stable mass, is ($m {}_{62}\text{Sm}^{150} = 150.36$):

$$(120) \quad nykl({}_{62}\text{Sm}^{150}) \rightarrow 150.36 / 150 = 1.0024$$

Then, his data, relative to the determined mass (125), will be as follows: $fmp(0.495655633)$, $fmn(0.506744367)$, $st^{sv} = 0.011088733$, $mp = 0.999305713$, $mn = 1.005445172$.

Therefore, the expected value of this mass, (${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$), for example:

$$(121) \quad m({}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}) \rightarrow 125nykl = 125.3$$

Here, it is necessary to recall the analytical connection of the data of Table 2 and the matrix of the unfolding of the gravitational background loop of the processes of compression and expansion of visible matter, according to the positions: (101 - 105). In particular, the definition of its content of the final periods: G and H, as a result of the positive compression limit (${}^{\downarrow}\Sigma$) from the position (102) to the position (103). In any case, the value of the reduced proton (${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$) corresponds to the content of invisible matter, that is, the proton of mirror nuclei: $mp = 0.999305713$. Whereas, its neutron of the diagonal combination of periods: (1- 4), ($mn' = 1.00130697$), corresponds to the square of the Helium nucleon:

$$(122) \quad nykl'\text{He} \rightarrow \sqrt{mn'}(1.00130697) = 1.000653272$$

In this case, it can be noted that the diagonal combination of the periodic composition of the horizontal layers of the functional structure of the nucleon gradation—the units of charge—determines the vertical step

angle of the "turn" sequence of the interaction between visible and invisible matter. This definition refers to the degree of transition (st^n), a number—the number field between the reduced proton and neutron of Samarium (${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}$):

$$(123) \quad st^n({}_{62}\text{Sm}^{125}) \rightarrow \ln(mn(1.005445172)) / \ln(mp(0.999305713)) = -7.818834714$$

For lovers of geometric constructions, not structural, but textural architecture of interactions of spatial objects, the given value of the degree of transition will be practically adequate to the sine of the negative neutron of the mirror nucleus of Oxygen (${}_{8}\text{O}^{16}$): $(\sin(stn)) - 1 \rightarrow -1.000617971 = mn({}_{8}\text{O}^{16})$.

Furthermore, according to Table 2, Promethium (${}_{61}\text{Pm}^{125}$) was discovered in 2025. Its mass is unknown, but its ghostly presence lasted for approximately three hundred and ten nanoseconds (>310 ns). Therefore, from Table 2, $m(124.9376632)$ also represents a nucleon corresponding to the invisible matter field:

$$(124) \quad \text{nykl}({}_{61}\text{Pm}^{125}) \rightarrow m(124.9376632) / 125 = 0.999501306 \leftrightarrow \text{nykl}({}_{61}\text{Pm}^{125})^{-1} = 1.000498943$$

In this case, one key feature of the entire contents of Table 2 follows. This is directly related to the law of conservation of mass. Thus, regardless of how the proton and neutron compositions change, the value of the reduced mass, as well as the nucleon, will remain constant. Consequently, taking into account the diagonal combinations of periodic parallel level layers, given the interaction values of visible and invisible matter, the functional content of the reduced mass value is determined. Thus, without going into details of the content of all the isotopes presented in Table 2, special attention should be paid to the compression limit ($\downarrow\Sigma$), when the charge number corresponds to the charge of the Tin isotope (${}_{50}\text{Sn}^{125}$). Officially, there are five of them, including the main one, of the same mass. Of particular interest are the third (2059.5(4) keV) and fourth (2623.5(5) keV) isotopes of this mass. With half-lives: (650(60) ns) and (230(17) ns), respectively. Is it possible that this is a matter of the cyclic state, when the decay product is the isotope itself? And this is not an isolated case for other masses. This element has quite a lot of stable isotopes and can be in the number and field of its nucleon. Indeed, the nucleon number of its atomic mass can belong to two values simultaneously - the number and the number field:

$$(125) \quad \text{nykl}({}_{50}\text{Sn}^{118}) \rightarrow m(118.71) / 118 = 1.006016949$$

$$(126) \quad \text{nykl}'({}_{50}\text{Sn}^{119}) / 119 = 0.997563025$$

This is explained by the fact that the numerical value of the established stable mass refers to a significantly shifted (z) definition of the number – the number field relative to the central symmetry of the unit between the mass numbers (118 and 119):

$$(127) \quad z \rightarrow (1 - 0.71) = 0.29 \leftrightarrow (0.71 / 0.29) = e'(2.448275862)$$

Here, the defined (e') gives the ratio of displacement fragments in the unit structure. This important indicator will be presented again here, as a mass-to-charge ratio, that is, to determine the functional fragment of the proton, for example: ($fmp \rightarrow (e')^{-1} = 0.408450704$).

By the way, the given fragment of the proton function: ($fmp = 0.408450704$), belongs to the static mass of Barium (${}_{56}\text{Ba}^{137}$). Its fragments of the proton function: ($fmp = 0.408426244$), the neutron function ($fmn = 0.592812442$). Nucleon number: $\text{nykl}(\text{Ba}) = 1.00238686 \leftrightarrow 1.0024$. Degree of freedom: $stsv = 0.184386199$. The value of this mass will be presented later in this topic.

Thus, position (126), which defines the nucleon of Tin: (${}_{50}\text{Sn}^{119}$), can be considered more acceptable for this definition. Moreover, the field number of this nucleon corresponds to the field number of the nucleon of stable Samarium (${}_{62}\text{Sm}^{150}$): $(120) \text{nykl}({}_{62}\text{Sm}^{150}) \rightarrow 150.36 / 150 = 1.0024$.

$$(128) \text{nykl}'({}_{50}\text{Sn}^{119})^{-1} \rightarrow \text{nykl}({}_{62}\text{Sm}^{150}) \rightarrow (126) \rightarrow 0.997563025^{-1} = 1.0024'(42928)$$

Then the mass of tin (${}_{50}\text{Sn}^{125}$) will have the following value:

$$(129) m({}_{50}\text{Sn}^{125}) \rightarrow 125\text{nykl}'({}_{50}\text{Sn}^{119}) = 124.6953781$$

For official quantum physics, these data may be paradoxical, in that the content of the expansion process, represented in Table 2, is due to a reduction in its charge and an increase in neutron mass, where the compression limit defines "cold" isotopes. Meanwhile, the law of thermodynamics presupposes the presence of a certain enthalpy or entropy in the processes of expansion or compression of any material. The author hopes that readers of this material will not confuse thermal expansion with the expansion of matter in the Universe. The final periodic composition of Table 2 relates to the charge of Molybdenum: (${}_{42}\text{Mo}^{125}$), the total mass of this table. In this case, an example of a critical mass is given, the state of which, for example, determines the lowest charge. These conditions, up to the critical mass state, are satisfied by the value of the unit space constant (e), distributed by the displacement (z) in the unit structure:

$$(129) z^e \rightarrow (1 - e^{-1}) \rightarrow e_1(0.632120559) - e^{-1} = 0.264241118$$

According to the periods ($97 \leftrightarrow 101$) in Table 2, these conditions violate the threshold limit of the distribution of the proton and neutron functions within the nucleon – unit charge, with the subsequent allocation of the degree of freedom (st^{sv}) as an adequate function of the proton. In this case, since the degree of freedom (st^{sv}) is a neutral value containing the "nodal" (nuclear) structure of the result of the interaction of the proton and neutron functions, it becomes a reactive substance in the limit of the compression process (${}^1\Sigma$). Thus, the numbers of reduced protons and neutrons in the three periods (98 – 10) relate to visible matter. The reduced values of the proton function fragments and the numbers of the degrees of freedom of these periods have insignificant differences. The ratios of these quantities, as a selective comparison, to the constant of the unit of space will be as follows:

$$(130) {}^1\Sigma(\text{fmp})^{98} \rightarrow 0.339191613^{-1} = 2.948186104 \leftrightarrow e_2 \rightarrow \ln(2.948186104) = 1.081190101$$

$$(131) (st^{sv})^{98} \rightarrow 0.32561147^{-1} = 3.071144883 \leftrightarrow e_3 \rightarrow \ln(3.071144883) = 1.122050418$$

$$(132) \ln[\sqrt{(e_3 / e_2)}] \rightarrow st^{sv}({}_{56}\text{Ba}^{137}) = 0.01854768$$

Table 3. In principle, these data determine the cyclic content of all known isotopes, starting, say, with Helium (${}_{2}\text{He}^3$) and ending with Helium (${}_{2}\text{He}^8$).

N	el	fmp	fnn
1	${}_{2}\text{He}^3$	0.666360472	0.334289528
2	${}_{6}\text{C}^9$	0.666360472	0.334568695
3	${}_{5}\text{B}^8$	0.624677078	0.358141104
4	${}_{8}\text{O}^{13}$	0.615058513	0.384903987
1440	${}_{3}\text{Li}^8$	0.378463782	0.610619551
1441	${}_{54}\text{Xe}^{143}$	0.379957097	0.614739873
1442	${}_{6}\text{C}^{16}$	0.377454020	0.628744327
1443	${}_{4}\text{Be}^{11}$	0.377298672	0.617398298
1444	${}_{54}\text{Xe}^{144}$	0.374677190	0.616608524
1445	${}_{3}\text{Li}^9$	0.374677190	0.626251977
1446	${}_{2}\text{He}^6$	0.374677190	0.620019780
1447	${}_{4}\text{Be}^{12}$	0.363317649	0.638037907
1448	${}_{2}\text{He}^8$	0.333027279	0.667622721

For example, the first four isotopes and the last nine corresponding chemical elements are taken, the sequence of which is determined by the atomic number and the most consistent numerical value. In this case, a pair and a triplet are presented that have common numbers of proton function fragments, but different neutron function fragments. These are Helium (${}_{2}\text{He}^3$) and Carbon (${}_{6}\text{C}^9$) at the beginning of Table 3. Xenon (${}_{54}\text{Xe}^{144}$), Lithium (${}_{3}\text{Li}^9$) and Helium (${}_{2}\text{He}^6$) at the end of Table 3. Helium (${}_{2}\text{He}^8$) completes the entire composition of this table. Similar large and small complexes of common values of proton or neutron function fragments (this also applies to isobars) in the composition of the entire array of isotopes are not uncommon. For example, the calcium isotope (${}_{20}\text{Ca}^{50}$), with a

proton function fragment ($fmp = 0.399669431$), leads the composition of thirty-seven isotopes, ending with thorium (${}_{90}\text{Th}^{225}$). In turn, lithium (${}_{3}\text{Li}^7$), with a proton function fragment ($fmp = 0.428234100$), determines the composition of twenty-five isotopes, ending with magnesium (${}_{12}\text{Mg}^{28}$). This is not due to some kind of numerical magic for "ignorant" lovers of all sorts of secrets.

First of all, all this knowledge is determined by the natural numbers themselves. In this case, this result is determined by the expansion phase: $((fmp + fmn) / fmp)^{-1}$, one of the interactions of the basic functions of the proton and neutron.

5.3. Topology of the distribution of visible and invisible masses of an object:

In a global definition, the entire proposed structure of Table A, the numerical structure of nucleons within the mass numbers 13–12, relates to visible matter, the sum of the periodic composition of the unit structure: ($mn = 124.6$), column (M:0.1). As has already been said, this is a fundamental shift relative to fundamental physical data, in particular, it relates to the structure of the nucleon unit: ($nykl \text{ H}^1 = 1.00794$) of Hydrogen (H^1). The main thematic analysis of the previous section provided the reader with visual information about two limits of the charge state of the same mass during expansion and, simultaneously, during compression.

Then, the invisible functional structure of this content will be represented by another limit of the unit composition, Table A, the numerical structure of nucleons within the mass numbers 13–12, the number thirteen (13). Table "B", the numerical structure of nucleons within the mass numbers 13–12.

As can be seen, the contents of the proposed table differ fundamentally from variant "A" of the presented data. In the case of table "B," the sum ($sum = 137.5$) of the nucleon periods in the column (mn) corresponds to the number of events of the base of the reduced proton number, where the event number (n) of a given quantity:

$$(133) \quad 'n(mp') \rightarrow 137.5^{-1} = 0.007272727 \leftrightarrow mp' \rightarrow \exp('n(mp')) = 1.007299238$$

Table "B", the numerical structure of nucleons within the mass numbers 13–12.

M:0.1	nykl	"A"(Pi / 6)'	$(1/2 \text{ nykl})^{-1}$	$\leftarrow L_n$		$1/2(n^{1/2} \text{ nykl})$	
m^n	$m^n / 13$	$1/2 \text{ nykl}$	$n^{1/2} \text{ nykl}$	$L_n(n^{1/2} \text{ nykl})$	$1/2(n^{1/2} \text{ nykl})$	(Pi / 6)	$\leftarrow L_n'$
13	1	0.5	1	0	0.5	0.95492966	-0.0461176
12.9	0.992308	0.49615385	1.00775194	-0.007722	0.503876	0.96233221	-0.0383956
12.8	0.984615	0.49230769	1.015625	-0.0155042	0.5078125	0.96985043	-0.0306134
12.7	0.976923	0.48846154	1.02362205	-0.0233474	0.511811	0.97748705	-0.0227702
12.6	0.969231	0.48461538	1.03174603	-0.0312525	0.515873	0.98524489	-0.0148651
12.5	0.961538	0.48076923	1.04	-0.0392207	0.52	0.99312684	-0.0068969
12.4	0.953846	0.47692308	1.0483871	-0.0472529	0.5241935	1.00113593	0.0011353
12.3	0.946154	0.47307692	1.05691057	-0.0553501	0.5284553	1.00927525	0.0092325
12.2	0.938462	0.46923077	1.06557377	-0.0635134	0.5327869	1.017548	0.0173958
12.1	0.930769	0.46538462	1.07438017	-0.0717439	0.5371901	1.02595748	0.0256263
12	0.923077	0.46153846	1.08333333	-0.0800427	0.5416667	1.03450713	0.0339251
sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum
137.5	10.57692	5.28846154	11.44733	-0.4349499	5.723665	10.9313949	-0.0723437

First of all, the entire content of the column: $(\frac{nykl}{mn / 13})$, refers to the numerical field of invisible matter. In contrast to variant: "A", in which the reorientation of the column: ($\leftarrow L_n$), refers to the internal content. In the case of variant "B", the reorientation of the column: ($\leftarrow L_n'$), refers to the external content. Thus, the spatial functional relationship of visible and invisible matter is realized in the range of shifted central superpositions of variant: ("A" = 12.6 \leftrightarrow 12.5), respectively, of columns (mn), and variant:

("B" = 12.5 ↔ 12.4). In the first case, visible matter, the value of the internal reorientation of the column: (← Ln), is the event number ('n₁), as the reduced base of the Hydrogen nucleon:

$$(133) \llbracket A \rrbracket 'n_1 \rightarrow 0.0026726 + (-0.0052956) = 0.0079052$$

In the second case, the event number ('n₂) of the external reorientation, column: (← Ln'), of the invisible matter of option "B", is the event number: ('n₂), of the sum of the columns: (mⁿ), of option "A". This again leads to a truly neutral "mass" of the imaginary Higgs boson (H⁰):

$$(134) \llbracket B \rrbracket 'n_2 \rightarrow (-0.0068969) + 0.0011353 = 0.00803217 \leftrightarrow ('n_2)^{-1} \rightarrow m(H^0) = 124.4993307$$

Subject description section: "3. Specific Topology of the Subject," position: (82)

A more detailed description of the proposed subject requires a specific goal for the practical solution of the given problem. Otherwise, a more detailed description of this subject would be endless.

So, the dot you've placed on a blank sheet of paper represents a rather complex functional structure of its content. Even the fact of the numerical relationship that the reduced mass of the functional neutron: (f_{mn} = 1.00198953), the mirror nucleus of Helium (₂He⁴), becomes the number of the nucleon of the number of numerical events: (nⁿ), the fundamental mass of the neutron: (m_n = 1.008665012), is not any convincing proof that what you have before you is, perhaps, something that can be some kind of answer to any question about the actual state of the Universe:

$$(135) 125(f_{mn}) \rightarrow n^n(125.2486912) \leftrightarrow \sqrt{n^n} \rightarrow (11.19145617 / 11) \rightarrow \sqrt{1.0174051106} = m_n (1.008665012)$$

In this case, the number: (11), represents the sum of the visible and invisible arguments of the structure of the unit volume: (Pi / 6).

In any paradoxical case, invisible or dark space is neutral matter. Diagrams: 1–14 of the fourteen isotopes in Table 2 represent the percentage of proton and neutron functions in the interaction structure of the internal and external contents of Dark Matter.

The functional interaction of the opposing values of the compression and expansion periods, determined by the internal and external spaces of Dark Matter, forms a predetermined "mixture" of their values within the degrees of freedom of these processes. As a result of the slight "flickering" of the minimal "contact" between the boundaries of internal and external space (Diagram 1), the enthalpy and entropy of the origin of Visible Matter are simultaneously formed. Moreover, as can be seen from the contents of the presented diagrams, the value of the neutron function, in this definition, will always be equal to fifty percent. The entire expansion process belongs to the function of the proton, resulting from the reduction of its charge. For spatial values, the defined content provided by Table 2 and the map of the unfolded spiral, "The distribution matrix of the gravitational background of the processes of compression and expansion of visible matter," pertains to the subject of cosmology: "Diagram 15."

Diagram 15 presents an inverse periodic level spiral model of the period of Consciousness of the beginning of Visible Matter, which is in the process of distributing future spatial structures formed as a result of the functional interaction of the internal and external contents of Dark Matter. In each definition of modular structures, starting with the variable pulsating "mixture" "A", corresponding to the value of the intermediate content of the column sum: (sum \leftrightarrow e-), the numerical events of the structure of the reduced electron, "The distribution matrix of the gravitational background of the processes of compression and expansion of visible matter", and ending with the "flickering" interaction of contact: (G \leftrightarrow H), the internal and external space of Dark Matter, the main definition is the negative base of the reduced nucleon of Oxygen: (nykl'O = -6.00943E-05):

$$(135) \exp(\text{nykl}'O) \rightarrow \exp(-6.0094E-05) \rightarrow 0.999939907 \leftrightarrow 16\text{nykl}'O = m {}_8O^{16} (15.99903852)$$

Naturally, the values of the data provided are determined by the established scale.

This is what concerns the metric of the mirror core of Oxygen (${}_8O^{16}$), which is necessary for the conditions of intellectual perception of the Dalton metric of the mirror core of Carbon (${}_6C^{12}$) of Visible Matter.

5.4. Topology of the beginning of a visible object:

As can be seen from the final diagram (14), the visual limit of the Dark Matter residue corresponds to fifty percent. Naturally, within the paradigm of the dilemma between visible and invisible space, as well as the hypothetical cause preceding the Big Bang, according to the data of the proposed topic, this is simply impossible. In this case, there is an additional percentage of the neutral "mixture" of the internal and external space of Matter. Only an ordinal count remains, in both cases, from one-half of the given spatial formations. Specifically, this concerns the constant functional interaction of the charge residue with the "neutral" phase, as the remainder of the fundamental functional interaction between the internal and external contents of Dark Matter space. This is explained by the fact that the physical basis of this interaction distributes known thermodynamic processes directly related to the various phase states of visible matter. Thus, from the perspective of the pathology of the subject, this functional interaction can be written as the base of one-half unit:

$$(136) \quad 1 / 2 = 0.5 \rightarrow \ln(0.5) = -0.69314718$$

In this case, the compression limits are: ($\downarrow\Sigma$), according to the phases: "A" and "B", of these values, the central superposition is determined: (50% \leftrightarrow 50%), (1/2), units of the relationship between the neutral "mixture" and the remainder of the charge:

$$(137) \quad \langle A \rangle \downarrow\Sigma \rightarrow ((-0.69314718 + 0.5) \times -0.69314718) = 0.1338794$$

$$(138) \quad \langle B \rangle \downarrow\Sigma \rightarrow ((-0.69314718 + 0.5) \times 0.5) = -pH^1(-0.0965736)$$

As you can see, as a result of compression, the reduced superposition structure determines two values of its content. The first, "A," corresponds to the second base of Pi. The second, to the negative value of the reduced density of Hydrogen: ($-pH^1 = -0.0965736$). In turn, the projection of the field, this density, the second result: "B," corresponds to the negative sum of the external composition of the unit: (~ 11), the reduced primary volume ($Pi/6$), the exponent of which corresponds to the base of the reduced nucleon number of Oxygen (nykl' O):

$$(139) \quad (Pi/6) \rightarrow (-pH^1)^{-1} = -10.3547978 \leftrightarrow \exp(-pH^1) \rightarrow (\exp(3.184E-05))^{-1} \sim \text{nykl' O } (0.9999682)$$

As a result of the expansion ($\uparrow\Sigma$) of the limits of the central superposition: (50% \leftrightarrow 50%), (1/2), the units of the relationship between the neutral "mixture" and the remainder of the charge:

$$(140) \quad \langle A \rangle \uparrow\Sigma \rightarrow (0.5 - (-0.69314718)) / 0.5^{-1} = 0.4190598$$

$$(141) \quad \langle B \rangle \uparrow\Sigma \rightarrow ((-0.69314718 - 0.5) / -0.69314718)^{-1} = -0.5809402$$

These data pertain to Bismuth ($_{83}\text{Bi}^{198}$). Here, the functional structure of matter undergoes a transformation between phases "A" and "B," the limits of compression and the limits of expansion as a result of the interconnectedness of the subject, when the linear metric of Oxygen transforms into the cubic metric of the "open" volume of the Carbon metric. From a topological standpoint, the nucleon mass number of the isotope Bismuth ($_{83}\text{Bi}^{198}$) corresponds to the cubic power of the Oxygen nucleon (nykl'O):

$$(142) \quad \text{nykl } ({}_{83}\text{Bi}^{198}) \rightarrow m(197.979201(30)) / 198 = 0.999894955 \leftrightarrow \sqrt[3]{0.999894955} = \text{nykl O } (0.999964984)$$

$$(143) \quad 16\text{nykl O} = m({}_8\text{O}^{16}) 15.99943974$$

From this definition, according to the primary volume matrix: "Primary Volume Structure Matrix", the first base: (Basis 1.) of this structure will be the Oxygen nucleon (nykl'O). The first phase: (Phase 1.) of this transformation will be the "open" volume according to the given value of the Bismuth nucleon number ($_{83}\text{Bi}^{198}$). Further, the second phase: (Phase 2.), defining the central superposition of the structure of the fu-

ture volume will correspond to the given value of Pi' . And finally, the first volume: (Volume 1.), completes the structure of the Bismuth nucleon content (${}_{83}\text{Bi}^{198}$):

$$(144) \text{Basis 1.} = \text{nyklO} \rightarrow \text{Phase 1.} = (\text{nykl O})^3 \rightarrow \text{Phase 2.} = \text{Pi}(\text{nykl Bi}) = \text{Pi}' \rightarrow \text{Volume 1.} = 0.523543774 \sim (\text{Pi}/6).$$

More details on the results of this transformation. First of all, according to positions (8) and (9), the base of the reduced Pi' , which determines the superposition of the relationship between the internal and external spaces of matter, will shift from two neutrons of the mirror nucleus of Oxygen: (${}_{8}\text{O}^{16}$), to two nucleons of Carbon: (nyklC), containing two nucleons of Nitrogen (nykl N):

$$(145) \text{Pi}' \rightarrow \text{Pi}(\text{nykl Bi}) = 3.141262645 \rightarrow \ln(\ln(\ln(\text{Pi}')))) = 2\text{nykl C}(-2.001910822)$$

$$(146) \text{nykl C} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}(-2.001910822) = 1.000955411 \leftrightarrow m({}_6\text{C}^{12}) \rightarrow 12\text{nykl C} = 12.01146493$$

$$(147) \text{nykl N} \rightarrow \sqrt{(\text{nykl C})} = 1.000477591 \leftrightarrow m({}_7\text{N}^{14}) = 14.00668628$$

6. Topology of the structure of gravity and microwave radiation of Dark Matter:

Continuing our analysis of the expansion process, in this case, it should be noted that for the conditions of the spatial structures of general matter, the interaction between the limits of inner and outer space is a variable definition. Thus, each mass structure, primarily according to Newton, is constantly undergoing opposing and counter-current processes of compression and expansion of its contents. In this case, the scale power of the gravitational structure is determined by the shift in the displacement limits of the fundamental functional fragments of the proton and neutron contained within the nucleon relative to the fundamental superposition of the given values of these data. In turn, the density of so-called microwave radiation is determined by the degree of mirroring of the interaction between the bases of the compression and expansion limits in the functional structures of phase definitions. In other words, if the limit of the shift in the composition of the nucleon structure relates to outer space, visible matter, then the expansion process reduces the charge number of the compression limit. If the limit of the shift in the nucleon's structure composition pertains to the internal space of invisible matter, then the expansion process increases the charge number of the compression limit. Consequently, a process of compression or expansion of values occurs: the proton's number or field as the internal content of space, and the neutron's number or field as the external content of space. Naturally, this definition lacks the scale of the cosmological concept of space, which is calculated by time, velocities, and distances between objects. It should also be noted that the discreteness of the objects defined by the author is not subject to any crystallization of space. The entire content of this subject represents the interaction of the internal and external contents of the shared space of dark matter, its visible and invisible functional structure. For example, the main periods of the functional structure of the expansion phase: $((A + B) / A)^{-1}$, the mass of (${}_{83}\text{Bi}^{198}$), relative to the Bismuth nucleon, are considered as a functional interaction of the internal and external contents of the space of matter. In this definition, in contrast to the interaction of the functional structure of the imaginary Higgs boson, the same phase, where the external expansion occurs due to the reduction of the value of the presented charges, the expansion of the functional structure of Bismuth (${}_{83}\text{Bi}^{198}$) occurs due to the increase of this charge to Polonium (${}_{84}\text{Po}^{198}$), phase: $((A + B) / A)^{-1}$, Table 4. Thus, the values of the columns $n(\text{mp})$ and $n(\text{mn})$ are the number of protons and neutrons. The result of the degrees of freedom, column (st^{sv}), is the third reduced basis of the primary volume matrix structure. This content presents the variable values of the interaction of number and number field, visible and invisible matter, contained within the periods of the column (Periods) of the functional structure of the expansion phase process $((A + B) / A)^{-1}$. It should be noted that from the seventh to the ninth period, the reduced values of the proton and neutron are defined as dark (invisible) matter.

Table 4.

Periods	fmp●	fmn○	st ^{sv}	n(mp)	n(mn)	mp'●	mn'○
1	0.4188566	0.5810477	0.16219118	82.93359917	115.04745	0.99919999	1.00041264
2	0.4188966	0.5810077	0.16211101	82.94153618	115.03952	0.999295617	1.00034362
3	0.4189367	0.5809676	0.16203083	82.94947395	115.03158	0.999391252	1.00027460
4	0.4189768	0.5809275	0.16195064	82.95741247	115.02364	0.999486897	1.00020557
5	0.4190169	0.5808874	0.16187045	82.96535176	115.0157	0.999582551	1.00013653
6	0.419057	0.5808473	0.16179025	82.97329181	115.00776	0.999678215	1.00006749
⁸³Bi¹⁹⁸	fmp●	fmn○				mp'●	mn'●
7	0.4190971	0.5808072	0.16171004	82.98123261	114.99982	0.999773887	0.99999843
8	0.4191372	0.5807671	0.16162982	82.98917418	114.99188	0.999869568	0.99992938
9	0.4191774	0.5807269	0.16154959	82.9971165	114.98394	0.999965259	0.99986031
⁸³Bi¹⁹⁸	fmp●	fmn○				mp'○	mn'●/○
10	0.4192175	0.5806868	0.16146936	83.00505959	114.97599	1.000060959	0.99979124
73	0.4217526	0.5781517	0.15639916	83.50700957	114.47404	1.006108549	1.00415827
⁸⁴Po¹⁹⁸	fmp●	fmn○				mp'●	mn'○
74	0.4217929	0.5781114	0.15631843	83.51500146	114.46605	0.994226208	1.00408817

The variable value of the neutron in the tenth period can be represented by its number and abundance field, depending on the integers of its quantity within the mass number. The proton and neutron become "visible" in the "critical" seventy-third period. The total mass of the nucleon remains constant. Polonium (⁸⁴Po¹⁹⁸) completes the proposed table in the seventy-fourth period with an "invisible" proton and a "visible" neutron. The structure of the functional interaction of all periods, as a result, relates to the quantum definition of microwave radiation, including the zero-valued gravitational fields due to which the known capture or emission of the product of the functional interaction of the inner and outer space of matter occurs, the "Interaction Matrix of Quantum Structure". Columns: $\Psi(-r \rightarrow) \leftrightarrow \Psi(r \rightarrow)$ – "flickering" generation of the mirror-image interaction bases of the polarized contact layer of the visible and invisible space of matter. Column: $B_V(T)$ – flickering intensity – the intermediate difference in the functional interaction structure of the polar outer layers, determining the periodic (variable) power of the charge density. In this column, during periods of zero value, a certain capture or emission of the product of the functional interaction of the internal and external space of matter occurs. In this case, as can be seen, as the number of periods increases, the power of zero values, the structure of the interaction of internal and external space, decreases. Meanwhile, the periodic density of the charge structure increases. This is the mirror image of the same charge ($z^{(+/-)}$). For example, the charge of the sum of the first four periods will be positive: ($z^{(+/-)} = 5.55112E - 17$). The charge of the sum from the eighth to the twelfth period is zero: ($z^{(+/-)} = 0$). The charge of the sum from the seventy-second to the seventy-fourth period will already be negative: ($z^{(+/-)} = -5.55112E - 17$). This feature depends on the positive or negative sign of the first number of the periodic composition of the charge structure power. Column: ($\Psi(r \leftrightarrow)$) – "visible" flickering, defined as the event number of the limit of the base of the mirror image of the functional relationship of the charge structure ($z^{(+/-)}$). Column (QDs) is the quantum tension of the outer layer of superposition: (points Pi), represented as the interaction of the internal and external space of matter. In this case, the periodic (pulsating) power of the charge ($\dot{P}^{r/z}$) is positive: ($\dot{P}^{r/z} = 5.55112E-17$), equal to the value of the neutron of the mirror nucleus of Helium (²He⁴) to the power of the third base of the structure of the matrix of the primary volume:

$$(148) \quad fmn \text{ } ^2\text{He}^4 \rightarrow \exp((\dot{P}^{r/z})^{-6}) = 1.00195504$$

Next, column: $\Psi(r \leftrightarrow)$, the progressive power intensity, the intermediate sum of the functional interaction of the polar internal layers' structure. Here, the value of the power generation intensity, for example, between the first and eighty-first periods, is determined by the unit of positive energy progress (⁺E):

$$(149) \quad ^+\text{E} \rightarrow {}_{81}\Psi(r \leftrightarrow) - {}_1\Psi(r \leftrightarrow) = 6.16142E-07$$

Interaction Matrix of Quantum Structure

Periods	$\Psi(-\vec{r})$	$\Psi(\vec{r})$	$B_V(T)$	$\Psi(\vec{r}^{\leftrightarrow})$	QDs	nykl He
1	-4.00859E-05	4.009E-05	5.55112E-17	8.01718E-05	1.00008018	1.00064158
2	-4.00897E-05	4.009E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.01795E-05	1.00008018	1.000641641
3	-4.00936E-05	4.009E-05	1.11022E-16	8.01871E-05	1.00008019	1.000641703
4	-4.00974E-05	4.01E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.01948E-05	1.0000802	1.000641764
5	-4.01012E-05	4.01E-05	0	8.02025E-05	1.00008021	1.000641826
6	-4.01051E-05	4.011E-05	0	8.02102E-05	1.00008021	1.000641887
7	-4.01089E-05	4.011E-05	0	8.02178E-05	1.00008022	1.000641949
8	-4.01128E-05	4.011E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.02255E-05	1.00008023	1.00064201
9	-4.01166E-05	4.012E-05	1.11022E-16	8.02332E-05	1.00008024	1.000642072
10	-4.01204E-05	4.012E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.02409E-05	1.00008024	1.000642133
11	-4.01243E-05	4.012E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.02486E-05	1.00008025	1.000642195
12	-4.01281E-05	4.013E-05	5.55112E-17	8.02562E-05	1.00008026	1.000642256
13	-4.0132E-05	4.013E-05	0	8.02639E-05	1.00008027	1.000642317
14	-4.01358E-05	4.014E-05	0	8.02716E-05	1.00008027	1.000642379
15	-4.01396E-05	4.014E-05	0	8.02793E-05	1.00008028	1.00064244
16	-4.01435E-05	4.014E-05	0	8.0287E-05	1.00008029	1.000642502
17	-4.01473E-05	4.015E-05	5.55112E-17	8.02946E-05	1.0000803	1.000642563
18	-4.01512E-05	4.015E-05	0	8.03023E-05	1.00008031	1.000642625
19	-4.0155E-05	4.016E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.031E-05	1.00008031	1.000642687
20	-4.01588E-05	4.016E-05	0	8.03177E-05	1.00008032	1.000642748
21	-4.01627E-05	4.016E-05	0	8.03254E-05	1.00008033	1.00064281
22	-4.01665E-05	4.017E-05	0	8.03331E-05	1.00008034	1.000642871
23	-4.01704E-05	4.017E-05	0	8.03408E-05	1.00008034	1.000642933
24	-4.01742E-05	4.017E-05	0	8.03484E-05	1.00008035	1.000642994
25	-4.01781E-05	4.018E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.03561E-05	1.00008036	1.000643056
26	-4.01819E-05	4.018E-05	0	8.03638E-05	1.00008037	1.000643117
27	-4.01858E-05	4.019E-05	0	8.03715E-05	1.00008037	1.000643179
64	-4.03283E-05	4.033E-05	0	8.06566E-05	1.00008066	1.000645461
65	-4.03322E-05	4.033E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.06643E-05	1.00008067	1.000645523
66	-4.0336E-05	4.034E-05	5.55112E-17	8.0672E-05	1.00008068	1.000645585
67	-4.03399E-05	4.034E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.06798E-05	1.00008068	1.000645646
68	-4.03437E-05	4.034E-05	5.55112E-17	8.06875E-05	1.00008069	1.000645708
69	-4.03476E-05	4.035E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.06952E-05	1.0000807	1.00064577
70	-4.03515E-05	4.035E-05	5.55112E-17	8.07029E-05	1.00008071	1.000645832
71	-4.03553E-05	4.036E-05	0	8.07107E-05	1.00008071	1.000645894
72	-4.03592E-05	4.036E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.07184E-05	1.00008072	1.000645956
73	-4.03631E-05	4.036E-05	5.55112E-17	8.07261E-05	1.00008073	1.000646017
74	-4.03669E-05	4.037E-05	-5.55112E-17	8.07338E-05	1.00008074	1.000646079
75	-4.03708E-05	4.037E-05	0	8.07416E-05	1.00008074	1.000646141
76	-4.03746E-05	4.037E-05	5.55112E-17	8.07493E-05	1.00008075	1.000646203
77	-4.03785E-05	4.038E-05	5.55112E-17	8.0757E-05	1.00008076	1.000646265
78	-4.03824E-05	4.038E-05	-1.11022E-16	8.07647E-05	1.00008077	1.000646327
79	-4.03862E-05	4.039E-05	5.55112E-17	8.07725E-05	1.00008078	1.000646389
80	-4.03901E-05	4.039E-05	0	8.07802E-05	1.00008078	1.00064645
81	-4.0394E-05	4.039E-05	0	8.07879E-05	1.00008079	1.000646512

In this case, the accumulated (potential) energy (${}^+E_p$), according to the composition of the periods, relative to the mass of the electron, will be the following value:

$$(150) \quad {}^+E_p \rightarrow 81({}^+E) = 4.99075E-05 \leftrightarrow (m_e / {}^+E_p) = 10.99835243$$

The number event (n') in this definition will correspond to the density of hydrogen (pH^1):

$$(151) \quad n' \rightarrow (m_e / {}^+E_p)^{-1} = pH^1(0.09092271)$$

The same indicator defines a nucleon, the content of which is four nucleons of Oxygen:

$$(152) \quad nyklO \rightarrow \sqrt[4]{(m_e / {}^+E_p) / 11} = 0.999962553 \leftrightarrow m({}_8O^{16}) \rightarrow 16nyklO = 15.99940085$$

Here, the number eleven contains the conditions of the basic structure of the unit according to the matrix of the primary volume as the sum of the linear and cubic contents: $(2 + 3 + 6 = 11)$, $(2^{-1} + 3^{-1} + 6^{-1} = 1)$. Further, according to point (152), the sequence of linear limits in the structure of the intensity of generation of the microwave background radiation power leads to the transformed value of the degree of freedom: ('st^{sv}) – the third base of the matrix of the unit volume, (Pi/6):

$$(153) ('st^{sv}) \rightarrow (149)^{-0.125} \rightarrow 0.16738251$$

In this case, the defined power: (-0.125), is the open volume of the first base (0.5), the first phase of the matrix of the unit volume: (Pi/6). This is the case when the structure of the unit is divided into functions of the proton and neutron. If, in the static content, the value of the third base, as the product of the compression limit of the functional interaction of the linear and cubic expression, that is: $(2 \cdot 3 = 6)$, is equal to six, where the nucleon, equal to unity: $(nykl \rightarrow (6 / 6) = 1)$, does not determine any displacement, then, under the conditions of the reduced base position: (153), this definition reveals the structure of the functional distribution of the values of the external and internal content of the space of matter:

$$(154) nykl' \rightarrow ('st^{sv})^{-1} \rightarrow 0.16738251^{-1} \rightarrow 5.97433990 / 6 = 0.99572332$$

First of all, the reduced nucleon is a number field, that is, a definition of dark matter. Consequently, its entire content is related to this value. It should be noted here that the content of a given nucleon simultaneously relates to two functional values of this definition. The first is the square root of the reduced neutron, and the second is the negative number of the fifth phase: (-Phase 5.), that is, the open volume of the microwave pulsation (breathing) of the "capture" and "escape" functions, compression and expansion, resulting from the interaction of external and internal space through the structure: (Pi/6), "Primary Volume Structure Matrix." For the first case, this is the value of the reduced neutron function, (mn')

$$(155) mn' \rightarrow (nykl')^2 = 0.99146492 \leftrightarrow 0.99146492^{-1} = 100860855$$

For the second case of the fifth phase, (-Phase' 5.):

$$(156) \text{-Phase' 5.} \rightarrow \ln(nykl') = -0.00428585 = 'n$$

The essence of the multitude of multifunctionality of the presented definitions, of the same meaning, is that as a result of functional interaction, a natural dialectic of evolutionary concepts is formed that forms the general structure of matter. In this case, the presented content leads to the negative limit of the superposition of the act of expanding the functions of the proton and neutron. Here, the given value, position (155), of the number and field of the neutron, is presented solely for clarity. The actual value, of course, is defined as only the field of this value. Thus, the limit of the base of the presented fifth phase, under the negative conditions of the quantum power (\dot{P}^m) of numerical events, is represented by another value, the value of the number of events ('n), where the power of this definition will be the field of the number of these events:

$$(157) \dot{P}^n \rightarrow 'n^{-1} = -233.325710$$

This definition leads to the relation of the expansion phase of the proton and neutron functions as opposite values of the structure of one nucleon ('nykl):

$$(158) 'nykl \rightarrow (-233.325710 / -2330 = 1.0013979 \leftrightarrow (mn / mp)$$

Therefore, this definition leads to the value of the proton number field (mp') of mirror nuclei:

$$(159) mp' \rightarrow \sqrt{('nykl^{-1})} = 0.99930178 \leftrightarrow (92)$$

In turn, the square of the base of the negative limit of the fifth phase: (-Phase' 5.), position (156), determines the information connection with the Oxygen nucleon (nykl O):

$$(160) \text{ nykl O} \rightarrow (\exp((-Phase' 5.)^2))^{-1} = 0.999963264 \leftrightarrow 16 \text{ nykl O} = 15.9994'1222$$

Thus, following the definition of the relationship between the mirror image of units of space (e''), positions (27) and (28), according to the structure of the unit of volume ($\text{Pi}/6$), relative to position (156) of the fifth phase (-Phase' 5), this value will be as follows:

$$(161) e'' \rightarrow [\exp((-Phase' 5(-0.00428585) \cdot \text{Pi}) / 6)]^3 = 0.99329041 \leftrightarrow 0.99329041^{-1} = 1.00675492$$

It should be noted that in this case, the mirror superposition projection contains a slight bias in its content in favor of the positive number field of this projection.

In any case, the quantum column tension (QCT), regardless of the number of periods, will correspond to the cyclic degree of the internal functional structure of the helium nucleon.

Conclusion:

This material provides the theoretical basis for a technology for modulating electric charges, resulting in the modular transmission of electrical energy according to a specified electrical power, converted into autonomous self-generation, the excitation and operation of which are directly transmitted by traditional electric current generators. This project is based on the "cold" superconducting synthesis of dielectric materials with an initial high variable electrical resistance.

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